

CODECO

Cognitive Decentralised
Edge Cloud Orchestration

D19: Use-case Deployment and Demonstrations v1.0

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Executive Summary

CODECO Deliverable *D19 – Use-case Deployment and Demonstrations* is a report provided in the context of WP5, with Task5.3 – Lab Experimentation. T5.3 focuses on the deployment of use-cases by different partners in their experimental premises, in an articulated way. The task supervises the overall proof-of-concept design, covering design aspects such as equipment, software, setup, actors, communication, and operation sequence design. The final aspect in this task concerns the design of demos by partners.

D19 details the use-cases' deployment and required validation exercises and software customization aspects on the current developed CODECO components. It also includes aspects such as usability, visualization, and experimentation progress. Finally, in Annex I, the template for the use-case demonstration plans is provided.

Keywords: Use-cases, Deployment, Evaluation, Demonstration

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Table of Contents

Executive Summary	3
1 Introduction	11
1.1 Document Scope	12
1.2 Document Structure	13
1.3 Document Dependencies	13
2 Use-Cases' Overview	14
2.1 CODECO Use-Cases	14
2.1.1 P1: Smart Monitoring of the Public Infrastructure	14
2.1.2 P2: Vehicular Digital Twin for Safe Urban Mobility	15
2.1.3 P3: MDS across Decentralised Edge-Cloud	17
2.1.4 P4: Demand Side Management in Decentralised Grids	19
2.1.5 P5: Wireless AGV Control for Flexible Factories	20
2.1.6 P6: Automated Crownstone Application Deployment for Smart Buildings	21
2.2 Key Deployment Challenges and Objectives	23
3 P1: Smart Monitoring of the Public Infrastructure	25
3.1 Use-Case Structure	25
3.2 Deployment Methodologies	27
3.2.1 Deployment Cases	27
3.2.2 Experimentation Cases	29
3.3 Software Customization	29
3.4 Evaluation Methodologies	29
3.5 Summary and Future Work	30
4 P2: Vehicular Digital Twin for Safe Urban Mobility	32
4.1 Use-Case Structure	33
4.1.1 Metrics of the Use-Case	34
4.1.2 Flow and Deployment Diagrams	34
4.1.3 Pre-conditions, Triggers and Post-conditions	35
4.2 Deployment Methodologies	36
4.2.1 Scenario	36
4.2.2 Infrastructure	37
4.2.3 Testing	37
4.3 Software Customization	37
4.4 Evaluation Methodologies	38
4.4.1 Key Performance Metrics	38
4.5 Summary and Future Work	39
5 P3: MDS across Decentralized Edge-Cloud	40
5.1 Use-Case Structure	40
5.1.1 Pre-conditions, Triggers, and Post-conditions	41
5.2 Deployment Methodologies	42
5.2.1 First Scenario: Virtual Single-Cluster Scenario	42
5.2.2 Second Scenario: Physical Single-Cluster Scenario	42
5.2.3 Third Scenario: Hybrid Multi-Cluster Scenario	43
5.2.4 Fourth Scenario: Full Physical Multi-Cluster Scenario	43
5.3 Evaluation Methodologies	44
5.4 Summary and Future Work	44
6 P4: Demand Side Management in Decentralized Grids	45
6.1 Use-Case Structure	45
6.1.1 System Structure and Workflow	45
6.1.2 Pre-conditions, Post-conditions, and Triggers	46
6.1.3 Technical Components of CODECO	47

6.1.4	Performance Metrics and KPIs	47
6.1.5	Summary of Technical Flow.....	48
6.2	Deployment Methodologies	48
6.2.1	Phase 1: Single Node – Initial Testing	48
6.2.2	Phase 2: Multi-Building Deployment	48
6.2.3	Phase 3: Multi-Campus Expansion	48
6.2.4	Phase 4: Full-Scale Deployment.....	49
6.3	Software Customization.....	49
6.4	Evaluation Methodologies.....	51
6.4.1	Validation Methodology.....	51
6.4.2	KPI Measurement Goals.....	52
6.4.3	Validation Environment.....	52
6.4.4	Comparative Analysis and Evaluation Outcomes.....	53
6.5	Summary and Future Work.....	53
7	P5: Wireless AGV Control for Flexible Factories	55
7.1	Use-Case Structure	55
7.2	Deployment Methodologies	58
7.2.1	Deployment of P5 User Journey 1	58
7.2.2	Deployment of P5 User Journey 2	59
7.3	Software Customization.....	59
7.3.1	Robotics Application Workload	59
7.3.2	Dashboard.....	61
7.4	Evaluation Methodologies.....	62
7.4.1	Operational Setup Control	62
7.4.2	Application Workload Control.....	63
7.4.3	Deployment of an Application and its Micro-Services.....	63
7.4.4	Runtime Management Evaluation	63
7.5	Summary and Future Work.....	64
8	P6: Automated Crownstone Application Deployment for Smart Buildings.....	65
8.1	Use-Case Structure	65
8.1.1	Crownstone Nodes Involvement	65
8.1.2	Crownstone Network Topology Awareness.....	66
8.1.3	Occupancy Awareness	66
8.1.4	Technical Overview of the Use-Case	66
8.2	Deployment Methodologies	68
8.2.1	User-Story 1: Automated Application Deployment	68
8.2.2	User-story 2: Topology-Based Application (Re)deployment	68
8.2.3	User-story 3: Occupancy-Based Application (Re)deployment	69
8.3	Software Customization.....	69
8.4	Evaluation Methodologies.....	70
8.4.1	User-Story 1: Automated Application Deployment	70
8.4.2	User-Story 2: Topology-Based Application (Re)deployment	70
8.4.3	User-Story 3: Occupancy-Based Application (Re)deployment	71
8.5	Summary & Future Work	71
9	Plan for the Demonstration of Use-cases	73
9.1	Phase 1: Detailed Demonstration Plans and Environment Setup.....	73
9.2	Phase 2: Event Preparation.....	74
9.3	Phase 3: Demonstration Execution.....	74
9.4	Phase 4: Result Dissemination and Evaluation.....	74
10	Summary and Next Steps.....	76
10.1	Application of CODECO Across the Use-Cases	76
10.2	Future Directions for Use-Case Implementations.....	78
	References	79

Annex 1: Use-Case Demonstration Plan Template	80
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List of Figures

Figure 1: The CODECO K8s framework and its components.....	12
Figure 2: P1 interactions between single-cluster applications and CODECO interfaces.....	26
Figure 3: P1 metrics and triggers in P1 Normal Flow.....	27
Figure 4: P1 intra-cluster task migration.....	28
Figure 5: P1 inter-cluster task migration.....	28
Figure 6: P2 functional view of the CODECO P2 use-case.....	33
Figure 7: P2 deployment diagram.....	35
Figure 8: P2 scenario facilities.....	36
Figure 9: P3 interaction scenario between the P3 application and the CODECO K8s framework.....	41
Figure 10: P3 final setup.....	43
Figure 11: P4 use-case architecture.....	46
Figure 12: P4 energy measurements through an ETSIT IoT infrastructure.....	50
Figure 13: P4 Kafka Producer.....	50
Figure 14: P4 energy measurements integrated in Prometheus.....	51
Figure 15: P5 system architecture, single cluster operation.....	56
Figure 16: P5 dashboard for Control of the AGVs.....	61
Figure 17: P6 Crownstone node inside a power outlet.....	65
Figure 18: P6 typical setup of a Crownstone network.....	67
Figure 19: Technical setup of use-case P6.....	68

List of Tables

Table 1: P1 KPI progress.....	30
Table 2: P2 Edge-Cloud continuum hardware.....	37
Table 3: P2 KPI progress.....	39
Table 4: P3 metrics.....	41
Table 5: P4 technical KPIs.....	52
Table 6: P4 sustainability KPIs.....	52
Table 7: P4 resilience KPIs.....	52
Table 8: P4 scenarios for testing.....	52
Table 9: P4 performance metrics.....	53
Table 10: P4 expected performance improvements.....	53
Table 11: P4 KPI progress.....	53
Table 12: P4 task progress.....	54
Table 13: P5 KPIs.....	57
Table 14: P5 basic node configuration.....	58
Table 15: P5 task progress.....	64
Table 16: P5 KPI progress.....	64
Table 17: P6 KPI progress.....	71
Table 18: ACM functionalities.....	77
Table 19: ACM functionalities applied in the CODECO use-cases.....	77
Table 20: PDLC functionalities.....	77
Table 21: PDLC functionalities applied in the CODECO use-cases.....	77
Table 22: SWM functionalities.....	77
Table 23: SWM functionalities applied in the CODECO use-cases.....	77
Table 24: NetMA functionalities.....	77
Table 25: NetMA functionalities applied in the CODECO use-cases.....	78
Table 26: MDM functionalities.....	78
Table 27: MDM functionalities applied in the CODECO use-cases.....	78

List of Acronyms and Definitions

Acronym	Meaning
ACM	Advanced Configuration and Management
AGV	Automated Guided Vehicle
AI	Artificial Intelligence
ALM	Almende
AMR	Autonomous Mobile Robot
AoI	Age of Information
API	Application Programming Interface
AR	Augmented Reality
AWS	Amazon Web Services
B2B	Business-to-Business
B2C	Business-to-Consumer
BESS	Battery Energy Storage System
BGP	Border Gateway Protocol
BGP-LS	Border Gateway Protocol Link-State
BLE	Bluetooth Low Energy
BTP	Basic Transport Protocol
C-ITS	Cooperative Intelligent Transport Systems
C-V2X	Cellular-V2X
CA	Cooperative Awareness
CAM	CODECO Application Model
CEI	Cloud-Edge-IoT
CNI	Container Network Interface
CO2	Carbon Dioxide
CPU	Central Processing Unit
CR	Custom Resource
CRD	Custom Resource Definition
CV	Computer Vision
DB	Database
DBMS	Database Management System
DDS	Data Distribution Service
DEN	Decentralized Environment Notification
DENM	DEN Messages
ER	Extended Reality
ETSIT	Escuela Técnica Superior de Ingenieros de Telecomunicación
EV	Electric Vehicle
FOR	fortiss
GB	Gigabyte
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GNSS	Global Navigation Satellite System
GPS	Global Positioning System
HTTP	Hypertext Transfer Protocol
HVAC	Heating, Ventilation, and Air Conditioning
ICMP	Internet Control Message Protocol
ID	Identification
IETF ALTO	Internet Engineering Task Force Application Layer Transport Optimization
IoT	Internet of Things

IP	Internet Protocol
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
K8s	Kubernetes
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LTE	Long Term Evolution
LTS	Long Term Support
MAC	Media Access Control
MAPEM	Map Extended Message
MDM	Metadata Manager
MDS	Media Distribution System
MEC	Multi-Access Edge Computing
MQTT	Message Queuing Telemetry Transport
NDN	Named Data Networking
NetMA	Network Management and Adaptation
OBU	Onboard Unit
P1	Pilot 1
P2	Pilot 2
P3	Pilot 3
P4	Pilot 4
P5	Pilot 5
P6	Pilot 6
PDLC	Privacy-preserving Decentralised Learning
PID	Prefix Identification
PV	Persistent Volume
PVC	Persistent Volume Claim
QoE	Quality of Experience
RAM	Random-Access Memory
RLT	Road Lane Topology
RMSE	Root Mean Square Error
ROCOF	Rate of Change of Failure
ROS2	Robotics Operating System v2
RPi	Raspberry Pi
RRL	Recurse Requisites List
RSSI	Received Signal Strength Indicator
RSU	Roadside Unit
RTT	Round-Trip Time
SCM	Service Configuration Management
SDN	Software-Defined Networking
SLAM	Simultaneous Localization and Mapping
SUMO	Simulation of Urban Mobility
SWM	Scheduling and Workload Migration
TCP	Transmission Control Protocol
TEE	Trusted Execution Environments
TID	Telefónica Innovación Digital
UART	Universal Asynchronous Receiver / Transmitter
UC	Use-Case
UGOE	University of Göttingen
UI	User Interface
UML	Unified Modeling Language
UPC	Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya
UPM	Polytechnic University of Madrid

UPRC	University of Piraeus Research Centre
USB	Universal Serial Bus
V2X	Vehicle-to-Everything
V2XaaS	V2X as a Service
VAM	VRU Awareness Message
VDMA	Verband Deutscher Maschinen und Anlagenbau
VKs	Virtual Kubelets
VRU	Vulnerable Road User
WP5	Work Package 5
WP6	Work Package 6
WP7	Work Package 7
YAML	Yet Another Markup Language

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1 Introduction

This deliverable provides a comprehensive overview of the work that was completed between months six (6) and twenty-four (24) of CODECO's project timeline, with a particular focus on the deployment and experimentation progress of the six innovative use-cases that are destined to showcase the valuable Cloud/Edge functionalities of the CODECO framework, including functionalities like latency and power efficiency optimization, real-time computation adjustments, as well as flexible and adaptive networking infrastructures from the far Edge to the Cloud. The use-cases are aimed at demonstrating the whole range of CODECO functionalities and features in a wide array of deployment configurations serving the needs of different stakeholders like infrastructure providers and Cloud/Edge application developers.

The initial CODECO containerized application orchestration framework composes of modular micro-services illustrated in Figure 1, to support the following aspects:

- **Automated configuration**, related with application setup and application runtime across Edge-Cloud, by taking into consideration compute, network, and data aspects. Automated configuration is handled by the CODECO Advanced Configuration and Management (**ACM**) component.
- **Data as a resource**. CODECO addresses, via its Metadata Manager (**MDM**) component data as a resource in the sense that available snapshots from the overall Edge-Cloud infrastructure, integrating different perspectives (application, user, system, data, network) at different instants of the CODECO operational workflow can be provided to different CODECO components, to assist in detecting relevant changes.
- **Dynamic scheduling and workload migration** is supported by the CODECO component Scheduling and Workload Migration (**SWM**). SWM integrates a novel concept by Siemens for seamless computing, including a novel scheduler for Kubernetes (K8s) that considers data-network-computation requirements to provide a best match between application requirements and available infrastructure (nodes, their computational and data properties, as well as network nodes and links), and to schedule and re-schedule application workloads across single cluster and federated cluster environments, considering application and user requirements.
- **Context-awareness and privacy preserving decentralised learning**, supported in the component Privacy-preserving Decentralised Learning (**PDLC**). CODECO relies on context-awareness to be able to achieve a joint data-network-compute orchestration, and on privacy-preserving decentralised learning and inference to best support readjustment of aspects such as the processing capability, computational resources, networking resources and interconnections in real-time.
- **Infrastructure adaptation based on a cross-layer data-compute-network approach**. Via the CODECO Network Management and Adaptation component (**NetMA**), CODECO assists in adapting not just computational (node resources) but also the networking infrastructure interconnecting such nodes.

Figure 1: The CODECO K8s framework and its components.

CODECO as a framework shall support the setup of applications across clusters (the so-called K8s application deployment) and the cluster runtime management operations for single and multi-cluster environments. Users relying on CODECO during an application deployment are named as **user DEV** in CODECO. Users relying on CODECO during the cluster runtime management are referred to as **user MGT**.

The document starts with a comprehensive summary of all CODECO use-cases. It then dedicates specific sections to each pilot, which encompass technical components such as deployment preconditions, triggers for CODECO activation, and postconditions within the operational environment. The CODECO use-cases include:

- **P1: Smart Monitoring of the Public Infrastructure**, led by the University of Göttingen (UGOE) and the City of Göttingen.
- P2: Vehicular Digital Twin for Safe Urban Mobility, led by i2CAT Foundation (i2CAT).
- P3: Media Distribution System (MDS) Across Decentralised Edge-Cloud, led by Telefónica Innovación Digital (TID).
- **P4: Demand-Side Management in Decentralised Grids**, led by the Polytechnic University of Madrid (UPM).
- P5: Wireless Automated Guided Vehicle (AGV) Control for Flexible Factories, led by fortiss (FOR).
- P6: Automated Crownstone Application Deployment for Smart Buildings, led by Almende (ALM).

The document concludes with a discussion of its findings and a description of the subsequent steps for the preparation of the second and final version of this deliverable.

1.1 Document Scope

This deliverable is consistent with the objectives of *Task 5.3 – Lab Experimentation*, which emphasizes on the coordinated deployment of use-cases by a variety of partners within their experimental environments. This task is responsible for the comprehensive proof-of-concept design, which includes key components such as equipment, software, setup, actors, communication protocols, and operational sequence design.

This deliverable includes the following:

- A detailed account of the structure, deployment strategies, and evaluation methodologies of all CODECO use-cases, as well as an explanation of the way in which CODECO will be employed in each instance.
- An overview of the next steps for each use-case, highlighting the current progress and outlining the remaining work.
- A roadmap for Task *T5.4 – Demonstrations*, as well as a summary of the progress made in CODECO's *Task T5.3 – Lab Experimentation*.
- A discussion on the plan for demonstrations of the CODECO use-cases.

1.2 Document Structure

This document is organized as follows:

- **Section 1 - Introduction.** In this section, an introduction to this document is provided as well as the goals for this deliverable.
- **Section - Use-Cases Overview.** The goal of Section 2 is to enrich the readers' understanding of the described use-cases based on a brief explanation of each one.
- **Section 3 – 8 CODECO Use-cases.** These sections correspond to the deployment and experimentation methodologies associated with each of the CODECO pilots. They are all adhering to the same structure. The latest structure of the corresponding use-case commences each section, which is followed by the deployment methodologies that will be employed in conjunction with CODECO to deploy the use-case. Subsequently, a concise overview of the various software applications that the use-case partners were required to develop is presented. The evaluation methodologies of each pilot, in addition to the experimentation and deployment plans that will be implemented to present the CODECO use-cases, are provided following the technical aspects. The summary and future work of the use-cases conclude each section, providing a brief discussion of the current achieved goals and the subsequent steps that must be taken to provide the pilots until the end of CODECO's lifetime.
- **Section 9 – Use-case Demonstrations.** This section highlights the planning of Task 5.4 – Demonstrations, whose purpose is to ensure a timely and consistent execution of the demonstration events for each of the use-cases. The section highlights the four phases of Task 5.4, from demonstration setup to evaluation.
- **Section 10 – Summary and Next Steps.** This section commences with a concise summary of the contents of this deliverable. Following this, a summary of the deployment and experimentation/validation is presented using various tables to give the reader a comprehensive understanding of the CODECO functionalities employed by each pilot. The subsequent steps of this deliverable are proposed to ensure that the next version is available by the last (36th) month of CODECO's lifetime.
- **Annex 1 – Demonstration plan template.** Provides the template adopted by T5.4 for the use-case demonstration plans (which will be provided in future deliverables).

1.3 Document Dependencies

The reader is strongly encouraged to read CODECO Deliverable D8 Use-cases [1] and CODECO Deliverable D10, CODECO architecture [2].

2 Use-Cases' Overview

Based on the updates, modifications, and restructuring made during the development of CODECO's workflow across one (1) cluster, a concise summary of the intermediate CODECO use-cases is given in this section. In the sixth month of the project's duration, CODECO generated a deliverable titled "D8: Fine-grained Use-case Design and Business Impact (v2.0)," [1] which is continued in the following subsections.

2.1 CODECO Use-Cases

2.1.1 P1: Smart Monitoring of the Public Infrastructure

In recent years, there has been a remarkable increase in the use of Smart City solutions aimed at benefiting both residents and visitors. Those usually are achieved by leveraging advanced technology and data analytics to monitor traffic, detect pedestrians and more. Data collected from various sensors and devices are transmitted and analysed to optimize traffic patterns, city planning and improve the quality of life for everyone. Now, with CODECO a more connected, efficient, and sustainable solution can be achieved. CODECO addresses the demand for handling large amounts of data in smart cities, including those with low latency demands. It is capable of orchestrating data flow across diverse features, both in terms of computation and networking. Besides, CODECO ensures a smooth and secure integration of data across Edge-Cloud environments. This ensures that data flows seamlessly and securely from Edge devices to the Cloud and vice versa, enabling end-to-end integration of smart city services. CODECO's decentralized approach to orchestration, along with its ability to deploy services in isolated, self-sufficient containers, offers great flexibility and adaptability. This means that smart city services can be deployed and executed in any environment, and the networking infrastructure can adapt to the needs of the services and the surrounding environment. This helps in creating a more resilient and adaptable smart city infrastructure.

The general purpose of P1 is to improve traffic flow and pedestrian safety in the city of Göttingen and assist in strengthening the existing Smart City concept through the implementation of a road monitoring and analytics system at the far Edge. This system comprises two parts: (i) traffic monitoring at the city periphery, and (ii) pedestrian distribution monitoring in the city centre. By collecting and analysing at the Edge valuable data on traffic and pedestrian behaviour, this use-case aims to optimize management, reduce congestion, and enhance overall pedestrian safety and comfort, while also providing valuable insights for city planning.

In the initial phase of the pilot, P1 will focus on two (2) specific zones in Göttingen: (i) the city periphery, which experiences high volumes of vehicular traffic, and (ii) the city centre, where pedestrian activity is most concentrated. For the initial phase of operation, these two (2) areas will be regarded as a single cluster that includes the cloud server(s) operated by the city and UGOE. The two areas will be configured as two (2) distinct clusters during the second phase.

The periphery of the city will be equipped with a combination of thermal cameras, computing units, and communication units. This will enable the real-time collection and analysis of traffic data, tracking vehicle counts and congestion levels. These insights will be used to optimize traffic flow, reduce bottlenecks, and improve overall traffic efficiency. In parallel, the city centre will see a combination of LiDARs, computing units, communication units, and the use of data analytic techniques to track pedestrian movement patterns and density. The data collected will be crucial for improving pedestrian safety, managing crowd flow, and informing city planning initiatives. The back-end data centre can obtain real-time processing results at the

Edge and visualize them to the public. As the pilot progresses, the data gathered will be evaluated and used to adjust traffic patterns, modify transport routes, and potentially redesign city layouts to better accommodate pedestrian and vehicular flow.

This pilot scenario, combining technological advancement and data-driven decision-making, is the first step towards transforming Göttingen into a truly smart city, enhancing the quality of life for its residents and visitors alike. Edge nodes co-located with the cameras represent K8s worker nodes; the control plane is expected to reside in the cloud. Hence, in the context of this use-case, CODECO shall be used to orchestrate (reallocate) resources across Edge-based environments, to assist in the degree of control decentralisation.

P1 considers the following three user-stories:

- **Transportation planning and management:** The government and municipalities will have access to real-time traffic analytics, including abnormal alarms, as well as long-term traffic pattern analytics. By automatically collecting and analysing data on traffic behaviour, they can gain insights that can inform decision-making and improve city planning, enhancing traffic safety and efficiency.
- **Property development and investment:** The infrastructure provider and deployer need to carefully consider the selection, deployment, and maintenance of the system, considering the feasibility and costs associated with each step. Once the system is deployed, the infrastructure provider conducts testing and validation to ensure that it is working effectively and providing the desired results.
- **Advertising and marketing:** Citizens will have access to real-time traffic information through downloadable apps or public boards, enabling them to plan their travel and make informed decisions about their routes.

A smart city application focused on traffic has the potential to revolutionize the field of traffic planning and management. Through the provision of real-time information on various traffic elements, including vehicles, pedestrians, cyclists, and motorcyclists, this technology can significantly contribute to urban traffic optimization, accident prevention, and various other aspects of transportation efficiency and safety.

Deployment Key Performance Indicators (KPIs):

- The number of installed CODECO frameworks ≥ 10
- Analytics Accuracy $\geq 75\%$
- Average number of processed frames per second per node increase at least 5%.
- Bandwidth cost: $< 10\text{G/month/LiDAR}$
- Rate of Change of Failure (ROCOF) $\leq 5\%$
- The data generated does not contain facial and other privacy-sensitive information.

Non-functional requirements:

- Privacy protection in video collection and transmission; General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) Compliance.

2.1.2 P2: Vehicular Digital Twin for Safe Urban Mobility

P2 makes use of the CODECO framework to support a Vehicular Digital Twin aimed to improve the safety of Vulnerable Road Users (VRUs) in urban environments. Any mobility oriented digital twin requires the extensive deployment of ultra reliable low latency services around the area it supports. Starting from the Vehicle-to-Everything (V2X) communication

capabilities to Computer Vision (CV) detectors capable of tracking all the moving parts within the mobility environment.

For this reason, the current use-case relies on V2X Roadside Units (RSUs) and cameras to gather all the necessary information to track vehicles and pedestrians and then feed it to the vehicular Digital Twin, which will detect dangerous situations or behaviours and alert them. The deployment and scalability of this service has challenges around the infrastructure side, where the information should be processed as close as possible to the V2X nodes and ensure low latency communications. This, in turn, translates to always having a fresh track of all the moving parts.

The pilot scenario focuses on the mobility environment of the interior and adjacent street of the Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya (UPC) campus known as “Campus Nord” in Barcelona, which is located next to i2CAT’s offices. This environment offers an interesting balance with walkable pedestrian zones that include bike lanes, as well as car lanes on the adjacent street. It encompasses a mix of various transportation modes, with VRUs playing a central role. However, VRUs can find themselves in dangerous situations when sharing spaces with cars, which addresses the use-case being presented. This scenario presents an ideal testing ground due to its size, allowing for the examination of multiple areas and their respective control measures. Additionally, it provides a diverse representation of all transportation modes commonly found in urban environments. Consequently, this scenario offers the perfect setting to assess and address the challenges associated with different modes of transportation, ensuring the safety and efficiency of urban transportation networks.

P1 considers the following four user-stories:

- **User Journey GOV:** The GOV stakeholder will have the availability to see a real-time low-latency digital twin of the moving entities around the designated urban public space. Check dangerous behaviour and immediate notifications when any incident happens (along with the place where the incident happened and how it happened).
- **User Journey ICT:** The ICT (both mobile communications and cloud providers) will use the CODECO framework to achieve reliability and low latency, which is crucial for the present use-case.
- **User Journey AR:** The AR stakeholders will be capable of ensuring through the proper research the viability of a system of Vulnerable Road User Awareness and provide solid information that reduces/eliminates incidents with that kind of users.
- **User Journey DEV:** The DEVs and especially the early adopters will run around the campus as VRUs and will receive an audio-visual notification. On the other side, other early adopters will be using conventional cars that will also notify collisions.

A V2X Vulnerable Road User awareness application has the potential to revolutionize the current approaches on road safety. By providing real-time information about the location and movements of VRUs such as pedestrians, cyclists, and motorcyclists, this technology can help preventing accidents and save lives. A summary of the business impact expected is as follows:

- One potential business case for this technology is in the public sector. Municipalities and other government agencies responsible for mobility could use this technology to monitor and reduce the number of incidents involving VRUs and other vehicles. By providing real-time data on the movements of these users, the application could help city planners design safer roads and intersections.
- Another potential business case is in the insurance industry. Insurance companies could use the data collected by the application to improve their revenue by accurately assessing risk and reducing the number of claims. The positional and camera data provided by the application could also help insurance companies more accurately determine fault in the event of an accident.

- The automotive industry is also a potential market for this technology. Car manufacturers are always looking for new features to include in their vehicles, and a V2X Vulnerable Road User awareness application could provide an extra layer of safety for drivers. This technology could be particularly useful for vulnerable vehicles such as bikes, electric scooters, and motorcycles.

Deployment KPIs:

- Latency from Cloud to the Onboard Unit (OBU) (using an RSU) < 20ms.
- Latency from OBU to Cloud (also using an RSU) < 20ms.
- Latency from Cloud to phone (Using conventional mobile network) < 20ms.
- Latency from phone to Cloud (Using conventional mobile network) < 20ms.
- Average Age of Information (AoI) < 70ms
- Average AoI Peak < 200ms
- Average AoI Penalty < 20
- Average AoI Penalty Peak < 50
- Processing time < 5ms
- Neighbour Awareness Ratio (<100m) = 100%
- Neighbour Awareness Ratio (100m - 300m) > 80%
- Effectiveness > 98%
- Awareness Ratio (<100m) > 95%
- Awareness Ratio (100m - 300m) > 50% (Depending on visibility)
- False Positives < 5%
- True Positives > 95%
- RSU Coverage area > 90%

Non-functional requirements:

- Privacy protection and robustness against attacks when emitting V2X messages.

2.1.3 P3: MDS across Decentralised Edge-Cloud

P3 focuses on the smart and efficient distribution of media content (e.g., video streaming, gaming, Augmented Reality/Extended Reality (AR&ER) across a multi-domain, multi-cluster Edge-Cloud. The use-case therefore leverages on a combined optimization of both connectivity (from the underlying transport network) and computational resources (supporting the MDS streamers and distribution logic). P3 promotes a tighter computational/networking integration and optimizes the overall resource usage while reaching a satisfactory level of Quality of Experience (QoE). To reach this, the use-case focuses on an interaction between a Media Delivery System (MDS), via CODECO, and the CODECO component NetMA which shall rely on a decentralized concept of the Internet Engineering Task Force Application Layer Transport Optimization (IETF ALTO) protocol to expose capabilities (e.g., topological information together with associated metrics, available resources, or functions) that promote joint adaptation.

The use-case is being deployed on a virtual environment with K8s, and considers the following user-story:

- **User Journey:** There are three (3) actors in this use-case. The primary actor is the application-service provider (and network capability client). There are also two (2) secondary actors: the application-service client, and the network operator. To be able to provide the information to the main user, the network operator obtains a Pid_file and cost_map generated with the inter-AS routing protocol Border Gateway Protocol (BGP) and

Border Gateway Protocol Link-State (BGP-LS) and it updates them showing information from the network. Prefix Identification (PID) associated to customer's Internet Protocol (IP) prefixes represent consumers of video streaming. PIDs associated to the connection of MDS streamers represent the potential sources of MDS traffic. As a main actor, the application-service provider, each time a client (application-service client) requests a service, wants to be able to obtain an updated network view to complement its internal view. The MDS logic requests ALTO to obtain network information before selecting the source to provide the data required: checking network and cost map information from both kinds of PIDs it is easy to match MDS streamers with customers. To select the more convenient streamer in each case, the use-case user can complement the Recurse Requisites List (RRL) with the view of the lowest cost between PIDs of MDS streamers and PIDs of customers. For example, for a given PID of customers, e.g., pid0:0a0a0a01, the more convenient streamer can be determined from the lowest cost of pid0:0a0a0a05 and pid0:0a0a0a06 (assuming the rest of considerations in RRL is similar). If the assignation is possible, it indicates to the application service client the IP of the server with the resource.

To fulfil the ever-changing demands of their clients, companies in the telecommunications sector are continually working to improve their services. Customer turnover is one of the most critical issues that service companies must deal with. The revenue and profitability of a firm can be significantly impacted by high customer turnover rates. Service providers are making investments in technology that can raise the quality of the customer experience (QoE) to deal with this problem. One way to reduce costs without a great investment is optimizing the use of the resources available. To achieve this, this use-case uses exposure capabilities to allow the network client to select the best path according to the nodes, the path characteristics and the internal client information. By this, the telecom operator increases service satisfaction by improving QoE. This solution allows better resource use, reducing delivery expenses and optimizing the capabilities available in both network and Edge-Cloud.

Deployment KPIs:

- The system can detect the path with the lowest latency.
- The system can detect if two paths have the same latency and select the one with a lower hop count.
- The system can detect which nodes have enough capacity to handle the resource request.
- The system can detect which network elements have enough bandwidth to transmit/process the resource requests.
- The network represented is the same as the real one.
- Network updates are correctly translated into topology maps.
- The path selected is the one with the maximum value of QoE.

Non-functional requirements:

- **Endpoint Authentication:** Even the information is not critical, an endpoint for authentication is needed to avoid data poisoning.
- **Interoperability:** System should be multi-vendor and do not have dependencies with the hardware/software used to deploy the pilot.
- **Maintenance:** System should be easy to maintain and update, having clear documentation about its parts, how it works and how to update it.
- **Reliability:** System should be able to detect a fall and recover from it. Also, it should have a failure-resistant deployment.

2.1.4 P4: Demand Side Management in Decentralised Grids

The fourth pilot P4 focuses on implementing an active demand response decentralized management system for building decarbonization. It aims to optimize energy usage, improve sustainability, and enhance the resilience of buildings by integrating renewable energy sources and enabling intelligent demand response actions. The use-case also emphasizes the joint orchestration of computational and networking resources to ensure efficient coordination and management of energy-consuming devices and the networking infrastructure within buildings. It focuses on achieving a holistic view of data on the Internet of Things-Edge-Cloud (IoT-Edge-Cloud) continuum, enabling comprehensive monitoring, analysis, and replication of energy-related data.

The CODECO framework leverages the capability of K8s to build a decentralized energy management system, by integrating worker nodes (which in this use-case have some correspondence with Edge nodes) and employing CODECO's developed tools like ACM, PDLC, and modular functionalities, P4 aims at achieving efficient resource utilization, scalability, resilience, and adaptability in energy management operations integrating the energy-related IoT systems and the computing needs.

The use-case will be implemented in three (3) University Campuses and singular buildings and considers the following two (2) user-stories:

- **User Journey #1:** UPM aims to be climate neutral by 2030. To this end, it seeks synergies between generation and energy consumption between its different campuses and its buildings. It leverages Edge computing capacity to make its associated generation and consumption forecasts, and scheduling and optimization models. From them, it decides how to group the different energy assets to achieve the best performance in terms of decarbonisation. This calculation is executed in the cloud and associated to the physical environment (cluster) defined, where IoT data are collected on the real-time operation to take the necessary corrective measures on planning.
- **User Journey #2:** UPM acting as an energy community, wants to offer energy aggregation (offering network flexibility and balance services to the system operator and distributors) and charging services for Electric Vehicles (EVs).

With increasing concerns about climate change and the need to transition to a low-carbon economy, the market demand for distributed energy management systems is growing. This demand is driven by factors such as government regulations promoting renewable energy adoption, rising energy costs, and the desire for energy independence and resilience. Market analysis reveals a significant potential for growth in the distributed energy management system market. The system caters to various sectors, including residential, commercial, and industrial, where energy consumers seek ways to reduce costs, improve sustainability, and contribute to environmental goals. Additionally, the integration of advanced technologies, such as IoT, Artificial Intelligence (AI), and blockchain, into these systems further enhances their capabilities and market attractiveness.

Key market players in the distributed energy management sector include energy service companies, technology providers, utilities, and energy aggregators. These players offer a range of solutions, including energy monitoring and control platforms, demand response management systems, and virtual power plant solutions. The impact of distributed energy management systems is multifaceted. They enable consumers to reduce their energy bills through optimized energy usage and by leveraging locally generated renewable energy. Additionally, these systems contribute to grid stability and resilience by balancing energy supply and demand in real-time, reducing the strain on centralized power infrastructure. Moreover, distributed energy management systems foster the integration of renewable energy

sources, accelerating the decarbonization of the energy sector. They facilitate the transition from a traditional centralized energy model to a decentralized and democratized energy system.

Overall, high-level market analysis reveals a growing demand for distributed energy management systems driven by energy cost savings, sustainability goals, and the need for resilient energy infrastructure. The market presents opportunities for innovative solutions and collaboration among stakeholders to transform the energy landscape towards a more sustainable and efficient future.

Deployment KPIs:

- Number of energy clusters created and modified per day = 20.
- Number of buildings involved > 3.
- Energy assets integrated > 100.
- Amount of kilowatt and kilowatt hours of the energy community = 30% UPM consumption.
- Amount of energy saved (not bought from the grid) \geq (10% – 20%).
- Carbon dioxide (CO₂) emissions reduction > 10%.
- Latency for energy function deployment < 1 minute.

Non-functional requirements:

- Trusted Execution Environments (TEE).

2.1.5 P5: Wireless AGV Control for Flexible Factories

There is today an increasing need to consider Automated Mobile Robots (AMRs), an example of which are AGVs in manufacturing environments, to support the heterogeneous and growing demand of material handling and logistics in flexible factory environments. While current AGV fleets are based on pre-defined task assignment and pre-defined paths, there is an urgent need to provide a more flexible control to support fleets with a larger number of AGVs, and to support an increasing number of tasks/goods to be transported. By reaching a higher level of autonomy, it is possible to increase overall efficiency while reducing operational costs. The integration of wireless technologies to support the control of AGVs, e.g., 5G, Wi-Fi 6/7, becomes highly relevant and shall be explored by CODECO. However, relying on wireless implies also that the control of AGV systems is prone to interference and intermittent connectivity, thus requiring a higher degree of adaptation which CODECO is expected to provide. Hence, in addition to the wireless connectivity aspects concerning interference mitigation, and synchronization, this use-case shall also demonstrate the CODECO capability to proactively adapt the overall network energy consumption and to mitigate interference and failures.

In this context, P5 shall explore AGVs handling goods within a warehouse, being subject to remote control and requiring real-time support. The use-case expects to be developed in three phases:

- Phase 1, single cluster, static control plane.
- Phase 2, single cluster (multi-master), mobile control plane.
- Phase 3, federated clusters.

AGVs shall therefore expect to carry different micro-services (containerized) for a single cluster. In this case AGVs shall correspond to K8s worker nodes, while the control plane shall reside on a static node. The AGV micro-services shall be managed by CODECO, being the

CODECO components placed across the control and data plane of K8s. On a second phase, the control plane shall also be deployed on a mobile node.

The use-case is being deployed on the fortiss IIoT Lab, interconnected to the CODECO multi-cluster infrastructure, and considers the following two user-stories:

- **Deployment of micro-services in an AGV fleet:** a user DEV wants to deploy a new CODECO offered application in P5 across an AGV fleet and wants also to manage its application workload with K8s/CODECO.
- **AGV Fleet control – Resilient infrastructure:** This user journey relates with the runtime management of the CODECO AGV Apps. The aim is to assist AGVs in autonomous navigation on indoor, blocked spaces. Key challenges concern energy optimization and support of intermittent connectivity. ICT stakeholders relevant for this use-case are mobile communications and Edge-Cloud providers.

The proposed solution in this use-case consists of CODECO and of a set of AGV fleet Apps to assist the deployment of the use-case, and to play with CODECO components. The key innovation aspects in P5 relate with the use of context-awareness and behaviour estimation to provide a higher degree of flexibility to the overall system, thus allowing control of AGVs to be managed in a decentralized way, expected to bring benefits in large-scale environments. In terms of performance, the application of CODECO in P5 is expected to improve scalability, resilience, and availability in comparison to K8s, adding also novel support in mobile environments.

Deployment KPIs:

- Time to completion of a task (latency): 20% reduction due to decentralized control.
- 10% reduction in the number of collisions.
- 10% improvement of energy efficiency of the network (overall involved nodes) and eventual network lifetime.
- Number of nodes supported (at least 5).
- Reduction in failures (resilience).

Non-functional requirements:

- **Scalability**, capability of CODECO to cope with an increasing number of application deployments across variable fleet sizes (large, heterogeneous) and towards mobile devices.
- **Privacy**, capability of CODECO to manage a varying infrastructure across a single or various locations (multi-domain environments).
- **Resilience** and availability, capability of CODECO to support five nines system availability in the verge of network interference and intermittent connectivity.

2.1.6 P6: Automated Crownstone Application Deployment for Smart Buildings

The domain of Smart Buildings has received increasing attention throughout the last decades, especially in the context of energy management, but also in relation to efficient and effective use of the built environment after the COVID-19 pandemic. In the sixth use-case, executed by ALM, the focus is on novel mechanisms for automated (re)deployment of smart office / smart building applications by means of an in-house developed technology called the Crownstone Platform. This platform was originally developed as a universal domotics solution for the consumer market. However, recently, ALM has decided to make a shift from Business-to-

Consumer (B2C) to the Business-to-Business (B2B) market, offering the Crownstone platform as a universal smart building technology for office environments. This poses completely new challenges on the technology, which are partially addressed in the use-case in this project. The Crownstone platform technology has been developed within the ALM group during the past years. The five (5) main constituents of the technology are:

- **Smart lustre terminals called Crownstone nodes**, which can be mounted inside power outlets. Next to several sensing, actuation, and networking capabilities, Crownstone nodes can run small apps called micro-apps, which are considered in this pilot as applications to be deployed. Hence, Crownstone nodes are a particular kind of worker nodes for CODECO.
- **Universal Serial Bus-sticks (USB-sticks) called Crownstone Bridges**, which are Crownstone nodes with their Universal Asynchronous Receiver / Transmitter (UART) connected to USB male socket, but without the technology to switch on/off devices and measuring power consumption. Bridges are used to connect a Bluetooth Mesh network to a Crownstone Hub.
- **Raspberry Pis (RPis) with a specific software stack installed, called Crownstone Hubs**. These are used to collect data from larger collections (at most 256) of Crownstone nodes, to process data, to deploy Microapps to Crownstone nodes, and to connect to the Cloud. The Crownstone Hubs are considered regular worker nodes in CODECO.
- **A cloud service called the Crownstone Cloud**, which serves to administer and exchange information about spheres (i.e., buildings / environments with Crownstone nodes that are connected to each other), rooms, Crownstone nodes, smartphones, and their relationships. The Crownstone Cloud runs in a worker node in the cloud.
- **A React Native based app called the Crownstone App**, which lets smartphones act as a beacon which can be detected by Crownstone nodes and provide a management dashboard for managing all details of the Crownstone platform within a single sphere. The Crownstone App is currently only being used for configuration purposes and does not play an active role in this pilot.

The Crownstone platform enables the deployment of multiple different applications, developed by multiple third parties, on a single infrastructure inside a smart building, thereby avoiding that every new end-user application installed in the building always introduces new hardware components to run the application on. The difficulty, however, is that there is a need to have better tools to manage and monitor the portfolio of installed applications in a single building or even over multiple buildings, as they share the same infrastructure. This use-case therefore focuses on application (re)deployment aspects on Crownstone networks.

The use-case will be implemented in the playground environment deployed at the main office of ALM. The office itself has three (3) rooms, in which two (2) Crownstone Hubs and twelve to twenty (12-20) Crownstone nodes are deployed. This setting is used to represent a single-office environment. The main user is the facility manager wishing to deploy applications in the office as well as to define service levels for those applications. P6 therefore considers the following three (3) user-stories:

- **Automated application deployment:** A facility manager wants to deploy applications on the Crownstone network in the office without logging into Crownstone Hubs, moving within Bluetooth range to Crownstone nodes, copy-pasting Media Access Control (MAC) addresses, etc. They set relevant parameters, including service levels, in a config file and CODECO will make sure the applications are correctly uploaded to the designated Crownstone nodes and hubs. This is a baseline user-story.
- **Topology-based application (re)deployment:** A set of applications is running on the Crownstone network in the office, while a topology change within the network occurs: a

new Crownstone is installed in the network. Without human intervention, CODECO recognizes the topology change and adapts the application orchestration, optimizing the distribution of applications over the nodes.

- **Occupancy-based application (re)deployment:** The varying presence of users in the office can tremendously influence the Bluetooth Low Energy (BLE) network statistics. Based on these statistics, CODECO (re)deploys applications on the Crownstone Hubs and micro-apps on the Crownstone nodes.

Deployment KPIs:

- Effort needed to deploy and expand local smart buildings infrastructures.
- Effort needed to develop and deploy distributed Edge-to-cloud AI applications.
- Effort needed to reconfigure far-Edge data processing applications.
- Ability to monitor and verify the correct behaviour of a Crownstone sphere.

Non-functional requirements:

- Non-invasiveness (e.g., Crownstone basic functionality always remains).
- Privacy-preserving with respect to data captured by sensors related to people in the building and their behaviour.

2.2 Key Deployment Challenges and Objectives

To ensure the successful deployment of CODECO use-cases across partner locations, it was essential to clearly define key design elements, such as equipment, software, setup, actors, communication protocols, and operational sequences. Task 5.3 was instrumental in this process as it refined the previously documented deliverable (D8) into a technically deployable format. The University of Piraeus Research Centre (UPRC) coordinated bi-weekly meetings among Task 5.3 members and ad-hoc discussions with pilot partners to achieve this transformation with consistent collaboration.

The six use-cases teams submitted elaborate responses to structured questionnaires between months seven and nineteen (7 and 19) of the project. These responses were subsequently reviewed and restructured to facilitate deployment. The technical documentation outlined in Sections 3 – 8 of the project report was established on the basis of these responses. The deployment specifics for each use-case are detailed in these sections, which are derived from the information collected through the following questionnaires and surveys:

- **Structure Questionnaire:** An Excel file containing seven comprehensive sheets, each of which addresses a distinct aspect of the use-case structure:
 - **KPIs:** Specifies the primary KPIs for each use-case.
 - **Sub-KPIs:** Deconstructs KPIs into quantifiable sub-KPIs, each of which is associated with objectives and methodologies for assessing its accomplishment.
 - **Actors:** Provides a comprehensive list of the actors involved in the use-case, establishing a connection between each sub-KPI and the appropriate participants.
 - **Equipment:** Defines the hardware necessary, including the minimum and maximum usage quantities, and associates the equipment with the corresponding actors.
 - **Software:** Outlines the software services that are involved, specifically mapping each service to the devices on which it will be executed.
 - **Operations:** Utilizes communication tuples to establish connections between software services, which are further supported by Unified Modeling Language

- (UML) diagrams to illustrate inter-service operations. This document also specifies the communication protocols and data formats that are used to transmit data.
- **Datasets:** A list of datasets that are used for training or validation, including their names and sizes.
 - **Methodologies Questionnaire:** The methodologies of each partner were thoroughly examined through this open-ended survey. The following topics were addressed: deployment strategies for achieving sub-KPIs, experimentation tools, related research, and evaluation approaches.
 - **Deployment Methodologies:** Outlines the procedure for the integration of CODECO into each pilot.
 - **Evaluation Methodologies:** Defines the methods for assessing sub-KPI outcomes to verify their success.
 - **Metrics Questionnaire:** A collection of metrics that are essential for the operation of each use-case.
 - **CODECO-Based Metrics:** Metrics that are collected from the components of the CODECO system.
 - **Application-Based Metrics:** Metrics that are gathered from external tools or the use-case itself, and they are used to support the broader functionality.
 - **Technical Details Questionnaire:** The technical preconditions and postconditions necessary for the deployment of each use-case are detailed in this document. It also specifies the environmental triggers that initiate CODECO's activation.

3 P1: Smart Monitoring of the Public Infrastructure

LiDAR plays a more and more important role in modern cities, especially reflected in the intelligent transportation system [2]. However, the density and volume of point cloud data generated by LiDAR are constantly changing with different periods within one (1) day. When heavy traffic is encountered, the increase in the amount of data or objects can lead to traffic analysis not in a timely manner, especially with a low-end Edge computer. In that manner, in this use-case, analytics task migration between different nodes or clusters by utilizing the CODECO framework is examined.

3.1 Use-Case Structure

In this use-case, LiDAR is used as a sensing device, and each LiDAR will be linked with an Edge device to form a node. The interactions between single-cluster use-case applications and CODECO components' interfaces are shown in Figure 2, where:

- **Link 1** includes ACM-MDM-1. It is used for data collection from K8s Custom Resource Definitions (CRDs) of other components and will be used in the MDM integration of the CODECO MDM operator.
- **Link 2** includes ACM-PDLC-2 and PDLC-ACM-2. ACM-PDLC-2 assists PDLC in obtaining CRDs from other components, while PDLC-ACM-2 delivers the infrastructure view results via a K8s Custom Resource (CR).
- **Link 3** includes ACM-SWM-1 and I-SWM-ACM-1. It involves utilizing CRD and CRs via the K8s Application Programming Interface (API) and ensuring accessibility and integration with CRs and operators managed by SWM and other CODECO components.
- **Link 4** integrates NetMA's CRs and operators.
- **Link 5** shares knowledge graphs from MDM to PDLC.
- **Link 6** enables SWM to receive suggestions from PDLC for workload placement decisions based on combined cost and behaviour estimation.
- **Link 7** allows SWM to request reservations from NetMA based on current scheduling/placement decisions.
- **Link 8:** Facilitates PDLC in providing infrastructure estimations to NetMA.
- **Link 9:** Integrates designated data types, such as data volume to be processed within a specific time interval and threshold values.

Figure 2: P1 interactions between single-cluster applications and CODECO interfaces.

The metrics and triggers of the use-case are illustrated via a Normal Flow (Figure 3). The user DEV wants to implement an application offered by CODECO in P1 and manage the application workload using K8s/CODECO. To start, the user utilizes the CODECO ACM User Interface (UI) to choose a pre-configured array of micro-services specifically assembled for this use-case. With the initial step, this use-case offers a fundamental array of available micro-services, point cloud pre-processing, point cloud analysis, and point cloud codec that are used for encoding and decoding the point cloud data. In this use-case, these micro-services are essential for every node.

Subsequently, the user is asked to provide a collection of specifications, for instance: (i) critical specifications like latency, (ii) number of nodes, (iii) communication type (such as 5G, Wi-Fi), (iv) data volume to be processed within a specific time interval, (v) maximum data volume that the node can process in real-time, and more related values. These categories contribute to the generation of the *CODECO Application Model (CAM)*, which is fundamental for appropriately scheduling resource utilization. Once this process is finished, ACM captures the Application Model and makes it accessible to other CODECO components using standard K8s methods. In a cluster, there will be one (1) node that acts as both a master node (CODECO Control Plane) and a worker node (executing microservices), and the rest of the nodes act as worker nodes. In that manner, all nodes in the cluster start point cloud capturing, pre-processing, and analysis. The "data_volume_in_time_interval" and "data_volume_threshold" have been set by the user DEV, and if the "data_volume" of a node is greater than or equal to the threshold, CODECO will be triggered to transfer part of the point cloud processing tasks from that node to another node in the cluster to help realize real-time point cloud analysis. Specifically, when the trigger condition is reached, MDM may

provide additional data information to PDLC, while PDLC may collect the node network status and remaining computation resources that may influence the orchestration decision provided by SWM.

Figure 3: P1 metrics and triggers in P1 Normal Flow.

3.2 Deployment Methodologies

3.2.1 Deployment Cases

3.2.1.1 Intra-Cluster Task Migration

In cooperation with the City of Göttingen, there is an agreement to select five to six (5-6) important traffic areas to do traffic monitoring. Each area is considered as one (1) cluster. As shown in Figure 4, there will be two to three (2-3) sets of CODECO nodes within a cluster, measuring different traffic directions. Within one (1) cluster, there is a high possibility of encountering such a traffic situation. That is, one direction with heavy traffic and another with light traffic. In that case, CODECO can assist in migrating part of the processing task to another worker node within this cluster.

Figure 4: P1 intra-cluster task migration.

3.2.1.2 Inter-Cluster Task Migration

Beyond the intra-cluster traffic case, each area could also encounter heavy traffic in both directions, which means the whole area encounters heavy traffic. So, there is a need to consider multi-clusters within CODECO's framework. If one (1) area encounters heavy traffic, it is better to migrate part of the processing task to nodes of another cluster. CODECO can bring both user journeys with a reduction of processing time of the traffic monitoring task. Thus, maintain the service in a timely manner even in heavy traffic areas or time. The inter-cluster case is represented in Figure 5.

Figure 5: P1 inter-cluster task migration.

3.2.2 Experimentation Cases

3.2.2.1 Testbed Deployment in Lab

The setup of the testbed deployment in lab contains a controlled environment with two to three (2-3) CODECO nodes (LiDAR sensors and NVIDIA Jetson Xavier¹ Edge devices) deployed in a small-scale testbed. The environment replicates real-world traffic scenarios with simulated or recorded traffic data. And the objective is to validate the ability of CODECO to dynamically migrate tasks within a single cluster and test inter-cluster task migration capabilities.

3.2.2.2 Cluster Deployment in Göttingen Traffic Areas

The setup of the cluster deployment in Göttingen traffic areas contains five to six (5-6) critical traffic areas selected, and each area is treated as a cluster with two to three (2-3) CODECO nodes. LiDAR sensors are positioned at strategic locations to cover different traffic directions. The corresponding environment contains real-world deployment with live traffic data. Nodes within a cluster communicate using Wi-Fi Direct², and clusters communicate via cellular networks [4] for inter-cluster task migration. The objective is to evaluate system performance under varying traffic conditions, including heavy traffic scenarios, in order to test the scalability and reliability of CODECO components in dynamic environments.

3.2.2.3 Multi-Cluster Testing

The setup of the multi-cluster testing contains nodes from neighbouring clusters that are integrated into a multi-cluster framework to test inter-cluster task migration. This setup involves handling workload transfers between nodes in adjacent clusters during heavy traffic. The objective is to validate the ability of CODECO to balance workloads across clusters efficiently, ensuring uninterrupted data processing and minimizing latency.

3.3 Software Customization

The following software tools are going to be used to ensure the use-case's functionality in cooperation with the CODECO framework:

- **Computing Tools (Pointpillars):** To enable point cloud analytics, an advanced computing tool is needed. The CUDA-Pointpillars³ model will be used for classifying objects from 3D point clouds.
- **Point Cloud Compression:** For point cloud processing, including transmission and storage, a reliable point cloud compression standard is required. Draco⁴ will be used for this task.
- **Database Management System (DBMS):** To save data of the use-case's application.

3.4 Evaluation Methodologies

To evaluate the utilization of CODECO in P1, two different scenarios are considered: 1) Independent data analytics on each node and 2) Resource sharing with CODECO. In the first scenario, each node will perform the object detection task by itself without offloading the data analytics tasks of any frame to another node. In the second scenario, nodes will offload data analytics tasks according to the resource capacities by using the CODECO framework. The aim is to increase the average number of processed frames per second-per node due to the usage of CODECO.

¹ <https://www.nvidia.com/en-us/autonomous-machines/embedded-systems/jetson-xavier-series/>

² <https://www.wi-fi.org/discover-wi-fi/wi-fi-direct>

³ <https://github.com/NVIDIA-AI-IOT/CUDA-PointPillars>

⁴ <https://google.github.io/draco/>

Before the deployment in the city, the aim is to deploy a testbed on UGOE campus to evaluate the data analytics tool, which is expected to achieve an accuracy of at least fifty percent (50%). In the following list, the measured KPIs (sub-KPIs) of the use-case can be found:

- **The number of installed CODECO toolkits:** Monitoring these toolkits in the backend to show which ones are online (connected) and which ones are not (disconnected).
- **Analytics accuracy:** After the deployment of the inferring model, an accuracy test will be performed on the validation dataset to ensure that the inferring result is correct for a performance of at least fifty percent (50%).
- **Data processing time:** Average number of processed frames per second-per node increases by five percent (5%) with CODECO in a heavy traffic area.
- **Minimize bandwidth costs:** Lossless compression of point cloud data (Compression Ratio 25%) to reduce bandwidth consumption.
- **ROCOF:** Collecting data on the number of failures of the system over a specified period and determining the total operational time. Then the ROCOF is calculated as the total number of failures divided by the total operational time.
- **Counter privacy issues (using LiDARs):** The use of LiDAR can accomplish this goal, and in addition, the dataset containing labels will be removed, after completing the deployment of the inferring model.

3.5 Summary and Future Work

Table 1 describes the sub-KPIs and the corresponding measurement goals regarding P1. It outlines the progress of achieving KPIs for P1, evaluating sub-KPIs such as the number of installed CODECO toolkits, analytics accuracy, data processing time, ROCOF, and privacy compliance.

Table 1: P1 KPI progress.

Sub-KPI	Measurement Goal	Achieved?	
		Yes	No
Number of installed CODECO toolkits	Above or equal to eight (8).		X
Analytics accuracy	Analytics accuracy is above or equal with fifty percent (50%).		X
Data processing time	Average number of processed frames per second per node increase by at least five percent (5%).		X
ROCOF	The ROCOF is less or equal with fifteen percent (15%).		X
Counter privacy issues (using LiDARs)	The data generated does not contain facial and other privacy-sensitive information.	X	

The future work of this use-case contains the deployment and testing of the CODECO framework in Göttingen traffic areas. It involves installing and integrating nodes in five (5) traffic zones, monitoring real-world data, and optimizing intra-cluster task migration to ensure system performance under varying traffic conditions. Network configurations are fine-tuned to minimize latency, and challenges related to hardware and environmental factors are addressed. Multi-cluster testing evaluates the framework's scalability and task migration capabilities across clusters under heavy traffic scenarios, with the goal of improving KPIs and optimizing system performance. Following are the next action points for this pilot.

Cluster Deployment in Göttingen Traffic Areas:

- Complete the deployment of CODECO nodes in all identified five (5) traffic areas in Göttingen. Each cluster will be equipped with two to three (2-3) nodes, strategically positioned to monitor key traffic directions. Ensure all deployed nodes are fully integrated with the CODECO framework, including components like PDLC, SWM, and NetMA.
- Conduct long-term monitoring to gather real-world traffic data. This data will be used to validate and fine-tune the CODECO framework in dynamic urban environments. Evaluate CODECO's intra-cluster task migration capabilities, ensuring that heavy traffic in one (1) direction does not compromise the overall system performance.
- Optimize network configurations (Wi-Fi Direct and cellular networks) to minimize latency during data transmission and task migration. Address any challenges related to hardware stability, environmental factors, or sensor accuracy during real-world deployments.

Multi-Cluster Testing:

- Expand the CODECO framework to enable seamless task migration between clusters.
- Simulate scenarios where multiple clusters encounter heavy traffic simultaneously to evaluate CODECO's ability to balance workloads across clusters. Test the scalability of the CODECO framework in managing increased traffic volumes across multiple clusters.
- Assess the effectiveness of multi-cluster task migration in improving KPIs and sub-KPIs. Use insights from these assessments to optimize the framework's performance and scalability.

4 P2: Vehicular Digital Twin for Safe Urban Mobility

As previously explained, the Vehicular Digital Twin for the Safe Urban Mobility use-case focuses on a scenario known as the Vulnerable Road User (VRU) protection use-case. Its primary objective is to ensure that, through vehicular communications and robust Edge-Cloud continuum connectivity, every VRU — whether a pedestrian, cyclist, or electric scooter user, among others — is accurately tracked while moving. This capability allows potential incidents to be anticipated and prevented, provided their communication devices are compatible with vehicular communication environments.

To achieve this, the solution deploys V2X communication modules across the Edge-Cloud continuum. These modules process all V2X messages, which contain critical information from the sensors of vehicles and connected road users. These sensors primarily include Global Navigation Satellite System (GNSS) devices that periodically sample location data. Sharing this data enables both road operators responsible for mobility efficiency and safety, as well as neighbouring road users, to have real-time awareness of the positions and movements of other vehicles and VRUs. This sharing of information fosters cooperative awareness and cooperative perception among all participants in the mobility environment.

Implementing a use-case that leverages shared data to prevent incidents imposes stringent requirements for low latency and high reliability. Within the CODECO framework, this translates into minimizing processing times, ensuring proper service scheduling within the Edge-Cloud continuum, and anticipating potential issues that could compromise the system's ability to handle large volumes of data generated by road users.

It is worth noting that such use-cases are traditionally implemented using Vehicular Ad Hoc Networks (VANETs) [5]. These networks operate as ad hoc point-to-point systems without relying on advanced technologies like K8s or the CODECO framework. However, VANETs typically require costly, dedicated hardware, which limits their widespread adoption due to affordability and complexity concerns. This is where the CODECO framework provides a transformative solution: it facilitates interoperability between conventional mobile networks and VANETs through robust infrastructure support. VRUs participating in this use-case connect via conventional communication networks to vehicular communication services running on the Edge-Cloud continuum. These services forward information between V2X-connected and conventional network users.

Additionally, a specialized module, the Digital Twin, is deployed within the Edge-Cloud continuum. It aggregates data from nodes in a specific area and uses this information to issue proactive alerts, anticipating potential problems.

The CODECO framework is also designed to optimize the performance of these distributed modules by continuously monitoring their operation, link performance, and anticipated demand surges. For example, as road users move, the latency between VRUs and Edge nodes may fluctuate. To maintain optimal performance, services deployed on one (1) Edge node may need to be rescheduled to another node. This dynamic rescheduling ensures the system remains efficient and reliable despite changing conditions. Further details on this process are provided in the next section.

4.1 Use-Case Structure

To elaborate on the concepts described in the previous section, the Vehicular Digital Twin use-case incorporates several modules that implement specific ETSI Cooperative Intelligent Transport Systems (C-ITS) protocols [6], which form the European V2X protocol stack [7]. Additionally, other modules are responsible for collecting and processing the information generated within the system. A detailed overview of the modules expected to be deployed is presented in Figure 6.

Figure 6: P2 functional view of the CODECO P2 use-case.

The functionalities of the nodes within the Edge-Cloud continuum are described as follows:

- **Geonetworking Service:** This service processes GeoNetworking network protocol [8] headers from messages sent and received within the Cellular-V2X (C-V2X) environment.
- **Basic Transport Protocol (BTP) Service:** The BTP service processes BTP headers for messages destined for the C-V2X environment. To process incoming messages, their GeoNetworking headers must first be handled, which is why a BTP service module must be connected to a Geonetworking Service.
- **VRU Awareness Basic Service:** This service processes VRU Awareness Messages (VAMs), which contain the position and trajectory of one (1) or more VRUs. These messages are highly compressed to efficiently convey this information.
- **Cooperative Awareness (CA) Basic Service:** The CA Basic Service processes cooperative awareness Messages, which share the position and trajectory of vehicles. Like VAMs, road users disseminate these messages periodically.
- **Decentralized Environment Notification (DEN) Basic Service:** The DEN Basic Service oversees the generation and processing of DEN Messages (DENMs). These urgent messages provide alerts about potential or existing incidents in the mobility environment.
- **Road Lane Topology (RLT) Service:** The RLT Service sends Map Extended Messages (MAPEMs), which contain high-definition maps of the mobility environment. These messages efficiently compress extensive geographical data from one to five hundred (100–500) bytes.
- **V2X as a Service (V2XaaS):** This module implements a protocol stack for VRUs connected via conventional IP networks. It collects GNSS measurements from smartphones, generates VAMs with GeoNetworking and BTP headers on the Edge-Cloud continuum, and sends UI instructions back to the smartphones. Additionally, it processes messages from the C-V2X environment.
- **V2X Forwarder:** This module relays messages between the C-V2X and IP-based network realms. Specifically, it facilitates communication between V2XaaS modules and Geonetworking modules in both directions [9].
- **Dynamic Map:** Functioning as the Digital Twin, the Dynamic Map aggregates data processed by other modules—such as Geonetworking, BTP, and CA Basic Services—to maintain real-time awareness of the positions and movements of connected road users. This enables it to detect potential issues or incidents and issue advisories to vehicles or VRUs. It also provides real-time data to the backend for road operators to monitor traffic.
- **Backend:** The backend receives data from the Dynamic Map and makes it accessible to users via the frontend.

- **Frontend Web Server:** This module serves the frontend using the Hypertext Transfer Protocol (HTTP) protocol. It operates independently of other modules and can be deployed separately if needed.

It is important to note that all the modules described for this use-case are scalable. For instance, multiple instances of a Geonetworking module can run on different Edge nodes simultaneously to handle surges in demand.

4.1.1 Metrics of the Use-Case

Before delving into the critical role of the CODECO framework in enabling this use-case, it is essential to understand its requirements. Since this use-case focuses on mobility safety, neglecting performance or failing to ensure information is delivered with the highest possible Quality of Service (QoS) could lead to severe or even fatal consequences. As a result, the key requirements of this vehicular use-case are centred around minimizing latency and maximizing reliability. These metrics are vital to ensuring that the system operates efficiently and effectively under all conditions. The specific metrics and performance targets are detailed in the following sections.

4.1.2 Flow and Deployment Diagrams

At the time of writing, the proposed deployment for this use-case involves a single cluster with the following components:

- **Infrastructure Side:**
 - A cloud-based solution.
 - Two (2) Edge nodes.
 - Two (2) RSUs, each directly connected to one (1) of the Edge nodes.
 - A Long-Term Evolution (LTE) or 5G Mobile Network
- **Client Side:**
 - Road users equipped with C-V2X-capable On-Board Units (OBUs).
 - 5G-capable smartphones.

This architecture is illustrated in Figure 7, which provides a schematic of the deployment. As noted in the previous section, all functional components will be dynamically scheduled based on the prevailing conditions. The figure also clarifies the roles played by each CODECO framework component, emphasizing that the PDLC component operates independently of the use-case-specific modules. Below is a brief explanation of how each component contributes to the deployment:

- **ACM:** The ACM component initializes and configures all use-case-specific and CODECO framework modules. It ensures that the deployment is seamless, and all components function cohesively.
- **SWM:** The SWM plays a critical role in deploying and managing components by scheduling their placement and migrating workloads as needed. Based on PDLC recommendations, it dynamically adjusts workloads across nodes to maintain optimal performance. For instance, protocol processing modules may initially be deployed on one (1) Edge node, but as client locations change, its latency may increase compared to other Edge nodes. The CODECO framework enables SWM to migrate critical functionalities to closer nodes, thereby ensuring the best possible performance.
- **NetMA:** NetMA monitors and manages communication between all functional components. It collects network-specific metrics, such as latency and throughput between nodes or pods, and shares this data with PDLC. These insights help optimize network connections, trigger configuration changes, or facilitate workload migrations, as necessary.

- PDLC:** PDLC gathers requirements and metrics from all components and provides directives to SWM (in the figure PDLC, coexists with SWM – thus it is not shown). It leverages heuristics to determine the optimal performance strategies based on the current infrastructure setup and proactively anticipates potential problems. By capturing insights from the network and system behaviour, the PDLC ensures seamless adjustments to maintain efficiency and reliability.

Figure 7: P2 deployment diagram.

4.1.3 Pre-conditions, Triggers and Post-conditions

On a technical level, the stringent requirements of this use-case, driven by its operational safety needs, translate into specific conditions and triggers that must be addressed during deployment and operation. The system must maintain latencies below thirty (30) ms, with the majority of latencies expected to fall between five to ten (5–10) ms. Additionally, the Aol [11] must remain below five hundred (500) ms, with an average Aol typically ranging between one to two hundred (100–200) ms, and packet loss must stay under five percent (5%).

Before deploying the use-case modules, it is crucial to ensure that the mobile network is properly configured to support reliable communication. The Road-Side Units (RSUs) must be connected to the cluster to facilitate seamless communication between the cluster pods and the C-V2X communication environment. Furthermore, all Edge and cloud nodes expected to handle workloads must be operational and correctly integrated into the system.

During operation, the CODECO framework will continuously monitor the system's performance. If any of the defined metric thresholds are breached, corrective actions will be

taken to restore optimal conditions. Additionally, the framework is designed to implement pre-emptive measures when metrics approach their critical limits, ensuring consistent performance and minimizing the risk of degradation.

Finally, as part of the postconditions, all metrics gathered during the operation of the use-case will be logged for further analysis. This data will be invaluable for evaluating performance, diagnosing any issues, and improving the system for future deployments.

4.2 Deployment Methodologies

4.2.1 Scenario

The use-case will be deployed in the i2CAT facilities. As seen in Figure 8, next to the i2CAT facilities there is a mix of both pedestrian sidewalks and roads, where vehicles and pedestrians can collide. In the same figure a red rectangle shows a key collision-prone section. Though P2, the pedestrians and vehicles will be warned of a possible up-coming collision. In terms of the CODECO framework, it must ensure that the V2X service will be available at all times and meeting the minimum requirements, specially focusing on latency and AoI.

In Figure 8, the route of a car (blue arrows) and of a pedestrian (green arrow) can be seen. These will be the key routes of two actors, but there will be more pedestrians and vehicles moving around the environment, possibly congesting the system in terms of network and computing. Here the CODECO framework will have to ensure that the system is still functioning and can provide timely warning to pedestrians and vehicles in the collision-prone area.

Figure 8: P2 scenario facilities.

4.2.2 Infrastructure

The use-case will be deployed on three nodes. each providing different computational capabilities. An NVIDIA Jetson Orin⁵, an NVIDIA Jeton Orin Nano⁶ and a Supermicro SYS-610C-TR rackable server⁷ will be used (Table 2). These three nodes will be interconnected completely, each being able to communicate with each other through exclusive Ethernet connections. Finally, a public cloud infrastructure will be possibly used to add more computing power and diversity to the infrastructure used, as it will provide higher compute power with lower network capabilities.

Two of the nodes (Jetson Orin and Jetson Orin Nano) will be connected to radio units compatible with V2X communication, either using Unex V2X modems⁸ or Cohda MK6 OBU⁹. These will provide the capability of being part of the ecosystem and communicating with the end-users (i.e., vehicles through V2X communication). The radio units will be connected through a dedicated, exclusive Ethernet or USB connection to the node.

The users equipped with smartphones will communicate through the mobile 5G network and will be directed to the node in the cluster.

Table 2: P2 Edge-Cloud continuum hardware.

Name	Central Processing Unit (CPU)	Random-Access Memory (RAM)	Disk
Supermicro SYS-610C-TR	Intel(R) Xeon(R) Silver 4316 20 Cores @ 2.30GHz	225 Gigabyte (GB)	3840 GB
Jetson Orin	Arm® Cortex®-A78AE 12 Cores @ 2.20GHz	64 GB	64 GB
Jetson Orin Nano	CPU Arm® Cortex®-A78AE 6 Cores @ 1.50GHz	8 GB	64 GB

4.2.3 Testing

To test the performance of the CODECO framework and its intelligent adaptability, custom created simulators that are able to mock the sending of V2X messages using the Simulation of Urban Mobility (SUMO) simulator¹⁰ will be used. Also, to artificially restrict the throughput or latency of a network link (i.e., Linux interface) the standard Linux networking tools (e.g., tc¹¹) will be exploited. Finally, to artificially load the nodes there will be usage of the Debian stress function¹² that allows for both RAM and CPU loading. These tools enable testing the performance of the CODECO framework for P2, as well as fine-tuning the infrastructure to its fullest potential.

4.3 Software Customization

For this use-case, there is a need to connect to specific radio units (e.g., V2X modems) that require custom-mode plug-ins. These plug-ins will need to be tailor-made and deployed simultaneously with the CODECO framework when the use-case is launched. Similarly, to ensure service reliability, there will be a scaling on the deployment based on key metrics. These metrics, exposed by the CODECO framework, will be measured and evaluated by

⁵ <https://www.nvidia.com/content/dam/en-zz/Solutions/gtcf21/jetson-orin/nvidia-jetson-agx-orin-technical-brief.pdf>

⁶ https://openzeka.com/wp-content/uploads/2023/03/jetson-orin-nano-datasheet-r4-web.pdf?srsId=AfmBOoo-k_K3MP35URslaCOYTL2xL_LAtJqIUhuf9BP-3nbGaexlV0R_

⁷ <https://www.supermicro.com/en/products/system/cloudcc/1u/sys-610c-tr>

⁸ <https://unex.com.tw/pdf/SOM-301E.pdf>

⁹ https://www.cohdawireless.com/wp-content/uploads/2022/09/CW_Product-Brief-sheet-MK6-OBu.pdf

¹⁰ <https://eclipse.dev/sumo/>

¹¹ <https://www.man7.org/linux/man-pages/man8/tc.8.html>

¹² <https://manpages.debian.org/testing/stress/stress.1.en.html#:~:text=stress%20is%20a%20tool%20that%20imposes%20a%20configurable,errors%20it%20detects.%20stress%20is%20not%20a%20benchmark.>

i2CAT to determine the appropriate scaling actions. In this stage, K8s Horizontal Pod Autoscaler¹³ will be exploited, which will monitor key metrics to scale the deployments of P2 appropriately.

4.4 Evaluation Methodologies

The evaluation of the present use-case will consider all the metrics and KPIs described in this section. These metrics and KPIs will not only be monitored during the full execution of the use-case but will also be compared against other proposed VRU protection use-cases. Unlike those alternatives, which rely on fixed topologies for deploying nodes and modules across the Edge-Cloud continuum, this use-case utilizes the CODECO framework.

4.4.1 Key Performance Metrics

The primary metrics used to assess the performance of the use-case are latency, Aol, jitter, and packet loss. Evaluating just one of these metrics in isolation carries the risk overlooking critical aspects of either reliability or latency. Therefore, all four metrics, along with their associated sub-KPIs, are taken into account:

- **Latency:** refers to the time taken for a packet to travel from one node to another. It is commonly measured using Internet Control Message Protocol (ICMP) messages, known as "pings," which calculate the Round-Trip Time (RTT) between two nodes. However, RTT does not always provide an accurate measure of packet delay between two nodes, as the delay may not be symmetric between the two directions (e.g., A to B vs. B to A). Additionally, most V2X packets are not transmitted via unicast, making traditional RTT measurements infeasible. For this use-case, latency will be measured using timestamped beacon packets periodically sent between nodes to directly assess the delay.
- **Aol:** Age of Information measures the freshness of information received by a node monitoring sensor data. In this use-case, Aol applies to Global Positioning System (GPS) devices installed on all road users, regardless of their type, and to the Dynamic Map distributed across the Edge-Cloud continuum. Each measurement will be timestamped with the time ($u(t)$), and Aol will be calculated using the formula: **Aol = t - u(t)**. This calculation will be performed directly within the Dynamic Map.
- **Jitter:** Jitter represents the variation in packet-to-packet delays and serves as an indicator of link stability. It is inherently derived from latency measurements and will be calculated using the same timestamped delay data.
- **Packet Loss:** Packet loss quantifies reliability by measuring the number of packets that fail to reach their destination. While protocols with acknowledgment mechanisms, such as Transmission Control Protocol (TCP), make packet loss easy to measure, non-acknowledged protocols like BTP or broadcast/multicast communications lack such mechanisms. In this use-case, packet loss will be estimated based on the expected periodicity of V2X awareness packets. Since these packets are sent at fixed intervals, packet loss can be detected when the number of received updates deviates from the expected count.

By considering these four metrics collectively, the evaluation will provide a comprehensive assessment of the use-case's performance, ensuring both latency and reliability are thoroughly addressed.

¹³ <https://kubernetes.io/docs/tasks/run-application/horizontal-pod-autoscale/>

4.5 Summary and Future Work

Table 3 illustrates the current KPIs that have been achieved, as determined by the current status of the use-case. In the near future, the KPIs that must be achieved using CODECO will involve validations that are based on the freshness of the information used and the awareness of the neighbouring ratios.

Table 3: P2 KPI progress.

Sub-KPI	Measurement Goal	Achieved?	
		Yes	No
Latency from Cloud to OBU (using an RSU)	Latency: Under twenty (20) milliseconds (ms).	X	
Latency from OBU to Cloud (also using an RSU)	Latency: Under twenty (20) ms.	x	
Latency from Cloud to phone (Using conventional mobile network)	Latency: Under twenty (20) ms.	x	
Latency from phone to Cloud (Using conventional mobile network)	Latency: Under twenty (20) ms.	x	
Aol	Average Aol: Under seventy (70) ms.	x	
Peak Aol	Average Peak Aol: Under two hundred (200) ms.		x
Penalty Aol	Average Aol Penalty: Under twenty (20).	x	
Peak Penalty Aol	Average Aol Penalty Peak: Under fifty (50).		x
Processing time	Processing time: Under five (5) ms.	x	
Neighbour Awareness Ratio (<100m)	One hundred percent (100%) ratio.		x
Neighbour Awareness Ratio (100m - 300m)	Above eighty percent (80%) ratio.		x

5 P3: MDS across Decentralized Edge-Cloud

The primary objective of the Media Delivery System (MDS) use-case is to establish a highly adaptable platform capable of ensuring swift responses to content requests. This platform serves as an abstracted solution for computation and connectivity, efficiently managing the deployment and utilization of Multi-Access Edge Computing (MEC) instances and caches, while seamlessly interconnecting them. In this scenario, the MDS provider possesses the expertise to deliver content to clients but may lack the capacity to deploy and manage numerous instances of APIs and caches or adapt its system in near real-time when necessary. CODECO addresses these challenges by handling deployment and interconnection complexities. This allows the MDS provider to focus solely on delivering content in response to client requests, making CODECO a critical enabler for the use-case.

5.1 Use-Case Structure

The MDS use-case consists of a complete multimedia content deployment environment. At this point of the project, and given that there is a single cluster ecosystem, a partial deployment of the use-case capabilities is going to be performed. In this partial deployment there is a focus on obtaining Edge metrics and integrating them into a customer database.

The use-case has three (3) main actors:

- The UC (Use-Case) user: this is an external code to CODECO, which will provide metrics to the Service Configuration Management (SCM) in a comparable way as the multimedia application would do in a real environment.
- The CODECO client: this client in turn has two parts, the external client (the use-case logic that runs outside the CODECO framework) and the code deployed in CODECO.
- CODECO Framework: in charge of launching, monitoring, and communicating the code defined in the CodecoApp.

Two main components will be used within the CODECO client code:

- MEC APIs: tool for obtaining metrics in Edge environments. It is the API that will obtain measurements exported by the user and that will complement the measurements of the CODECO framework.
- Client Database (DB): CODECO client's own database that integrates the metrics extracted by the different MEC instances.

In its interaction with the CODECO framework, the code associated to the use-case will have to be deployed having preferably the MEC component in the Edge nodes and the DB component in the cloud nodes. These nodes will have to communicate with each other through the CODECO framework, and during this first phase of the project no specific relocation is required to improve performance, being deployment and intercommunication the main features needed for the first release.

This interaction between CODECO client and CODECO framework is defined in Figure 9, where the MEC APIs are deployed in Edge nodes and communicated between CODECO, but exporting the metrics to the external client using an external communication (dotted line).

Figure 9: P3 interaction scenario between the P3 application and the CODECO K8s framework.

Among the metrics that this use-case will use are included specific metrics such as the distance between the user and the API, the connected users, the zone and the network areas. This information is managed directly by the application without going through CODECO's databases, so no special data management is required. On the other hand, it will also read information related to the environment, such as available link capacity, node bandwidth, link latency or storage capacity available at each node.

This information is summarized in Table 4.

Table 4: P3 metrics..

Metric	Source	Description
Users	MEC P3 code	Query location information about a specific UC user or a group of UC users.
Zones	MEC P3 code	Query the information about one or more specific zones or a list of zones
Subscriptions area	MEC P3 code	Retrieves information about the subscriptions for this requestor.
Bandwidth available	CODECO	Max bandwidth available for data transfer.
Memory available	CODECO	Memory available at each endpoint where the cache deployment will occur.
Jitter	CODECO	Average variation in the latency between instances deployed.

5.1.1 Pre-conditions, Triggers, and Post-conditions

In order to correctly perform the use-case, CODECO is expected to support the code by providing orchestration and monitoring of the different deployments, supporting new requests for scaling or reconfiguration (**ACM**); that the deployment is not static, being able to migrate deployments to other nodes without causing a drop in service (**SWM**); intelligent decision making, being able to anticipate network mishaps (**PDLC**), real-time node data collection, enabling optimal decision making (**MDM** and **NetMA**); and secure and transparent connectivity between the different components of the use-case deployed in CODECO (**NetMA**).

The preconditions of this use-case are mainly related to the environment where the system will be deployed:

- **Preparation of the environment:** both Edge and cloud devices must be properly connected and initialized, with sufficient capacity to run CODECO. The minimum number of nodes in each cluster is three (3).
- **Network connectivity:** In addition to connectivity through CODECO, there must be the possibility of establishing connections between clients outside the CODECO framework. This network must be monitorable, either through network protocols or the use of a Software-Defined Networking (SDN) controller.

In the P3 use-case there are two main triggers to take into account, both related with the QoS provided to the clients:

- **Appearance of service requests:** The MEC APIs detect an increase in media file requests that involve scaling or reconfiguration of current Edge caches.
- **Network connectivity issues:** Failure rate or latency variation increases abnormally in one area and requires service to be diverted to another.

The post-conditions of the use-case include the following:

- **Optimization of internal communications:** communications between caches are reduced by having a more optimized deployment compared to the default option.
- **Improved KPIs:** A reduction in latency in communications with customers is expected, as well as in the storage capacity required for the caches.
- **Scalability and adaptability:** The use of CODECO should help to predict network problems, avoiding service outages or performance bottlenecks.

5.2 Deployment Methodologies

The deployment and testing process for this use-case will be divided in four (4) scenarios: the initial testing in a virtualized single cluster scenario, the deployment in a physical single-cluster scenario, the multi-cluster scenario with virtual nodes and the multi-cluster scenario with physical Edge-Cloud nodes. The methodologies will include continuous testing with an incremental deploy to enhance integration and optimization.

5.2.1 First Scenario: Virtual Single-Cluster Scenario

In this stage the code will be tested with virtual nodes using the KinD (K8s in Docker) virtualization tool. The setup will include three (3) CODECO nodes (two worker nodes and a master node) and the main goal is to study the needs and dependencies between the UC and the CODECO framework.

For this first stage two (2) applications are going to be deployed that are interconnected using CODECO: the MEC APIs, that will have one (1) replica in a worker node; and a Mongo database, that has no requirements on where to be deployed.

In this first stage, the main objective is to test that the components are successfully deployed and there is connectivity between them.

5.2.2 Second Scenario: Physical Single-Cluster Scenario

In this second stage, it is expected to test the code in a more realistic environment. The scenario chosen for this is an environment with three (3) physical compute nodes, all with Ubuntu 22 operating system. In this scenario, the aim is to prove that the tests performed in a KinD environment work correctly in a physical environment, where more problems associated with the configuration, or the environment may arise.

The applications deployed in this environment are the same as in the previous scenario, and the validation of this environment is the current state.

5.2.3 Third Scenario: Hybrid Multi-Cluster Scenario

Making use of the advances achieved in Phase 2, a deployment in multi-cluster environments is going to be performed, complementing the previous deployment in a physical environment with a virtualized one. The necessary tests are performed to evaluate the dependencies and needs of the code in relation to a multi-cluster CODECO. The code presented here will include the use of ALTO servers, which integrate network information from network protocols such as BGP as well as from other data sources such as SDN controllers, allowing visibility of the network beyond CODECO. This information would be integrated with that of the MEC APIs to obtain a complete view by the user.

5.2.4 Fourth Scenario: Full Physical Multi-Cluster Scenario

In this last stage the tests performed are going to be integrated in a completely physical environment, with two (2) Edge nodes and one (1) cloud node in each cluster. In addition, in this stage consideration will be taken on a scenario with at least four (4) nodes routed outside CODECO. The code to be used consists of one (1) instance of the MEC API, one (1) instance of ALTO, one (1) integration database and one (1) Edge cache in each cluster.

Figure 10 shows the basic schematic of this final scenario, where the Edge devices will be PI 5 raspberries, and the cloud devices are Ubuntu 22 Linux servers.

Figure 10: P3 final setup.

The ultimate goal of these tests will be to fully validate the use-case by verifying the supremacy of using CODECO versus a static scenario.

5.3 Evaluation Methodologies

To perform a successful evaluation of the use-case, checks will be made from the post-conditions, which require a discrete review in the form of closed-ended questions (e.g. “has the preconditions been met?” “Yes/No”).

To do this, the same scenario of requests and resources will be used in two (2) different contexts: the default deployment in a pure K8s environment and the deployment in CODECO. From these scenarios and using external monitoring to CODECO (tools such as *tcpdump* and *top* to evaluate the use of network and compute resources respectively) a comparison will be done on whether the use of CODECO means an improvement in these three (3) cases.

To evaluate the first post-condition (optimization of internal communications), the bytes sent between the deployments made in K8s and CODECO will be measured, seeing how this deployment affects the number of interactions between these components. In the case that the required interactions are reduced, it means that CODECO is deploying the resources in a more efficient way than K8s by default.

In scalability and adaptability, the behaviour of deployments in a resource-tight environment as well as in a connection-irregularity environment will be evaluated. If the scaling of the caches, as well as the distribution of these is faster than in the default scenario, reducing the number of services drops or bottlenecks, the post-condition will be considered as fulfilled.

Finally, an evaluation of the KPIs associated to the use-case will be performed, through the improvement of latency metrics between user and caches, reduction of caching errors and reduction of the capacity needed to provide service to the clients.

All tests will be performed with scripts that will simulate client connections, as well as with scripts that will generate network disturbances, being possible to recreate these disturbances in both scenarios equally.

The scenario used for validation is the scenario presented in the fourth (4) deployment phase.

5.4 Summary and Future Work

Currently the use-case is finishing stage 2, with the deployment in a physical single-cluster environment. At this stage, the deployment of the use-case components is going well, being too early to see the efficiency of the deployment compared to the raw K8s environment as it is a very small scenario. The code is able to connect internally and receive the requests from the clients.

The next steps are to evaluate more diverse scenarios, with Raspberry Pi devices with limited capabilities. This will be followed by the evaluation of scenarios three (3) and four (4) presented previously, in parallel to the developments in the CODECO multi-cluster phase.

6 P4: Demand Side Management in Decentralized Grids

This pilot focuses on decentralized energy management to optimize energy consumption, integrate renewable energy sources, and enhance sustainability across distributed infrastructures. It involves deploying a scalable system to monitor, predict, and adapt energy usage dynamically. The pilot begins with single-building deployments and expands to a multi-campus scale, particularly within UPM's facilities (e.g., Moncloa, Sur, and Madrid campuses). The use-case aims to demonstrate improved **energy efficiency (5–10%)**, reduced **carbon emissions (5–10%)**, and enhanced **operational flexibility** through real-time monitoring and optimization of diverse energy assets such as photovoltaic systems, Battery Energy Storage System (BESS), and EVs.

CODECO highlights this use-case by showcasing its **Edge-to-Cloud continuum**, scalability, and modular architecture to address real-world challenges. The phased deployment strategy demonstrates how CODECO efficiently adapts to growing energy management complexities while maintaining seamless orchestration across nodes and clusters. CODECO's ability to integrate predictive analytics, load balancing, and demand-side response solutions emphasizes its innovative approach to managing energy dynamics. By aligning the use-case with measurable KPIs such as energy savings, latency (below 3 minutes), and reduced environmental impact, CODECO positions itself as a key enabler of sustainable and intelligent energy systems.

The CODECO framework is particularly useful in this pilot because of its modular components and real-time capabilities. **ACM** ensures efficient deployment and reconfiguration of energy nodes, while **MDM** centralizes real-time energy data for predictive insights. **PDLC** delivers dynamic predictions for energy demand and resource allocation while maintaining data privacy. **SWM** supports energy-aware task scheduling to optimize resource usage, and **NetMA** ensures reliable, low-latency communication across nodes. Together, these components enable CODECO to optimize energy consumption, integrate renewable resources seamlessly, and provide a scalable solution for decentralized energy management, addressing both environmental goals and operational needs.

6.1 Use-Case Structure

6.1.1 System Structure and Workflow

This pilot follows a structured multi-layer architecture with key components operating across Edge and cloud environments.

The deployment integrates energy monitoring nodes distributed across buildings, targeting general utilities (e.g., Heating, Ventilation, and Air Conditioning – HVAC systems) and specialized energy assets.

The **flow diagram** (Figure 11) highlights:

- **Data Acquisition Layer:** IoT-based sensors monitor energy consumption, grid parameters, and renewable generation in real-time.
- **Processing Layer:** Real-time data is collected, processed, and fed into predictive models at the Edge or cloud.

- **Orchestration Layer:** The CODECO components (ACM, MDM, SWM, NetMA, PDLC) optimize energy usage and task scheduling dynamically across distributed systems.

Figure 11: P4 use-case architecture.

This use-case is divided into the following four (4) phases:

- **Phase 1:** Single building proof-of-concept to validate energy monitoring and forecasting capabilities.
- **Phase 2:** Deployment expands to multiple nodes within a campus (e.g., UPM, Escuela Técnica Superior de Ingenieros de Telecomunicación – ETSIT).
- **Phase 3:** Integration across multi-campus infrastructures (Moncloa, Sur, Madrid).
- **Phase 4:** Full-scale deployment to test CODECO’s scalability in heterogeneous environments.

6.1.2 Pre-conditions, Post-conditions, and Triggers

Before CODECO starts, the following aspects must be met (pre-conditions):

- **System Setup:** IoT sensors, communication links, and distributed computing resources must be deployed and initialized across nodes.
- **Infrastructure Availability:** Edge nodes and cloud resources must be provisioned for orchestration and processing tasks.

- **Data Collection:** Energy data (e.g., consumption, photovoltaic systems generation, load profiles) must be collected and ingested into CODECO's components.

The triggers to set the CODECO operation are:

- **Energy Demand Fluctuations:** Sudden changes in energy demand trigger dynamic load balancing and task redistribution.
- **Renewable Generation Variability:** Variations in photovoltaic systems photovoltaic systems generation activate predictive analytics to adjust grid resource allocation.
- **Fault Detection:** Network or system anomalies trigger CODECO's fault-tolerant mechanisms for reconfiguration.

Once CODECO completes a change, the following conditions are expected (post-conditions):

- **Energy Optimization Achieved:** The system dynamically optimizes energy consumption and reduces peak load stress.
- **Improved KPIs:** Realized efficiency improvements (5–10%), latency constraints (under 3 minutes), and carbon footprint reduction (5–10%).
- **Resilience and Adaptability:** The deployment scales seamlessly to accommodate additional energy assets or nodes.

6.1.3 Technical Components of CODECO

The CODECO framework supports this use-case through its modular components:

- **ACM** orchestrates the deployment of energy monitoring nodes and cloud-Edge computing resources. ACM is also used for system reconfiguration for scalability and fault-tolerance.
- **MDM** collects and integrates real-time energy data from IoT sensors and provides data enrichment and feeds insights into predictive models for decision-making.
- **PDLC** delivers energy forecasts using machine learning models without centralizing sensitive data and enables load balancing and proactive task scheduling for energy efficiency.
- **SWM** dynamically redistributes tasks to optimize energy usage based on demand and available resources and is expected to contribute to energy-aware scheduling, prioritizing low-energy workloads during off-peak hours.
- **NetMA** monitors and optimizes communication latency for data exchange between nodes and ensures reliable real-time transmission of energy data for decision-making.

6.1.4 Performance Metrics and KPIs

The success of the use-case is measured using the following performance metrics:

- **Energy Efficiency:** Five to ten percent (5–10%) reduction in energy consumption through dynamic optimization.
- **Carbon Footprint:** Five to ten percent (5–10%) reduction in emissions achieved by integrating renewable energy sources.
- **Latency:** Under three (3) minutes for deployment and reconfiguration of system nodes.
- **Scalability:** Ability to manage nodes and assets across multiple campuses without performance degradation.
- **Resilience:** Fault detection and reconfiguration mechanisms ensure system stability in case of node failures.

6.1.5 Summary of Technical Flow

In the following list, the flow of the fourth pilot is explained, in a step-by-step manner:

- **Data Acquisition:** IoT sensors monitor energy parameters and send data to CODECO's framework.
- **Data Processing:** MDM enriches and feeds the data into PDLC for forecasting and analytics.
- **Optimization:** SWM redistributes energy tasks, and ACM orchestrates resource allocation dynamically.
- **Network Management:** NetMA ensures seamless communication between nodes for real-time decision-making.
- **Outcome:** CODECO achieves efficient energy optimization, integrates renewables, and ensures system scalability across Edge-Cloud infrastructures.

6.2 Deployment Methodologies

The deployment of this use-case within the CODECO project follows a structured, phased approach designed to validate scalability, adaptability, and efficiency across progressively larger environments. The methodologies include Edge-to-cloud orchestration, real-time monitoring, and integration of energy optimization tools. In the following subsections the phases of the deployment strategy are analysed.

6.2.1 Phase 1: Single Node – Initial Testing

- **Objective:** Validate the CODECO framework and components in a controlled environment.
- **Setup:**
 - Deployment on a **single building** (pilot environment) with energy monitoring nodes installed.
 - IoT sensors collect real-time energy consumption data from general utilities (HVAC, lighting) and specialized energy assets (photovoltaic systems panels, battery systems).
 - Testing focuses on real-time data ingestion, energy forecasting, and dynamic load optimization.

6.2.2 Phase 2: Multi-Building Deployment

- **Objective:** Scale the deployment to multiple nodes across a campus to assess integration and coordination capabilities.
- **Setup:**
 - Deployment across **four (4) buildings** within the ETSIT campus at UPM.
 - Each building integrates energy monitoring nodes and Edge resources for local processing.
 - Real-time orchestration and optimization occur at the Edge.
 - Network performance and latency are measured to ensure seamless communication.
- **Key Metrics:** Latency, energy efficiency, and resilience of orchestration across multiple nodes.

6.2.3 Phase 3: Multi-Campus Expansion

- **Objective:** Validate CODECO's scalability and adaptability in a **heterogeneous environment**.
- **Setup:**

- Deployment extends to **multiple campuses** within UPM, including Campus Moncloa, Campus Sur, Madrid facilities.
- Each campus operates energy monitoring nodes, and Edge resources are orchestrated centrally.
- Predictive analytics (PDLC) adapt energy optimization dynamically based on local consumption patterns and renewable generation variability.
- **Components Used:**
 - **ACM** manages the distributed deployment of nodes.
 - **PDLC** adapt energy optimization dynamically based on energy balance.
 - **NetMA** ensures low-latency data exchange between campuses.
 - **SWM** optimizes workload scheduling dynamically to reduce energy costs.

6.2.4 Phase 4: Full-Scale Deployment

- **Objective:** Demonstrate the full CODECO capabilities in a large-scale, real-world environment.
- **Setup:**
 - Integration of all nodes across UPM campuses, forming a distributed network of energy assets.
 - Each campus contributes data, optimized locally at the Edge.
 - CODECO's resilience and fault-tolerant mechanisms are validated under large-scale, multi-cluster deployments.
- **Testing Focus:**
 - **Scalability:** Ensuring orchestration efficiency as nodes scale.
 - **Resilience:** Testing system performance under node failures or network disruptions.
 - **Energy KPIs:** Measuring energy efficiency and CO2 emissions reductions.

6.3 Software Customization

This use-case should deal with these open issues:

- CODECO lacks inherent mechanisms to seamlessly process and integrate highly heterogeneous energy data from multiple sources. The use-case will develop custom pre-processing pipelines to normalize and standardize data across sources before feeding it into MDM. It will create an intermediary data integration layer to bridge communication between the data sources of the use-case and CODECO's orchestration tools.
- CODECO does not natively account for domain-specific constraints in energy management, such as regulatory requirements, peak load tariffs, or grid stability thresholds. The use-case aims at developing domain-specific algorithms and provide energy triggers to the framework to be used.

Regarding the software developed from UPM for the use-case, the most remarkable contributions and their use are listed below. The software is based in three (3) main parts, two (2) are situated on the Raspberry Pi and one (1) is located on a K8s pod. A brief description of this software is given in the next paragraphs.

On the embedded system (Raspberry Pi) there is a low-level C++ code that communicates with sensors nodes using the Modbus protocol over the serial RS485 standard. The code retrieves energy measurements from the sensors, formats them into a JavaScript Object Notation (JSON) data, and sends them to the next stage. An example of C++ code execution is shown in Figure 12.

Figure 14: P4 energy measurements integrated in Prometheus.

6.4 Evaluation Methodologies

The evaluation of the energy use-case revolves around validating the effectiveness, scalability, and efficiency of CODECO's integration into decentralized energy management.

6.4.1 Validation Methodology

The evaluation employs a structured methodology to validate the system across various levels of deployment and scales. The process includes the following stages:

1. Real-Time Testing and Monitoring

Objective: To validate CODECO's capability to collect, process, and respond to real-time energy data.

Key Validation Steps:

- Monitor latency from data acquisition to actionable decisions.
- Validate the accuracy of predictive analytics models, such as photovoltaic systems generation and energy demand forecasting.
- Measure the efficiency of task execution across Edge and cloud environments.

2. Incremental Scalability Testing

Objective: To assess performance as deployment scales from single node to multi-node environments.

Key Validation Steps:

- Measure system performance metrics, including latency, energy optimization, and fault tolerance, across an increasing number of nodes.
- Validate orchestration stability under heterogeneous conditions, such as variable workloads and renewable generation inputs.

3. Comparative Benchmarking

Objective: To compare CODECO's performance with baseline centralized energy management systems.

Key Validation Steps:

- Assess improvements in energy efficiency and carbon footprint reduction.

- Evaluate decision-making latency and system response under stress scenarios, such as peak demand.

6.4.2 KPI Measurement Goals

The evaluation methodology employs **sub-KPIs** defined in the structure questionnaire to measure the impact and success of the use-case. These are grouped into **technical**, **sustainability**, and **resilience** metrics. Table 5, Table 6, and Table 7 showcase all the related sub-KPIs, describing their targets and measurement methods.

Table 5: P4 technical KPIs.

Latency	
Target	Decision-making latency is under three (3) minutes for Edge-to-cloud communication.
Measurement	Time taken from data ingestion at Edge nodes to orchestration decisions made in the cloud.
Energy Forecast Accuracy	
Target	Prediction accuracy above ninety percent (90%) for energy demand and photovoltaic systems generation.
Measurement	Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) of predictions against actual energy usage data.
Load Balancing Efficiency	
Target	Reduce peak energy load by ten percent (10%).
Measurement	Comparison of peak loads before and after dynamic load redistribution.

Table 6: P4 sustainability KPIs.

Energy Efficiency	
Target	Achieve five to ten percent (5–10%) reduction in energy consumption.
Measurement	Total energy consumption before and after CODECO deployment.
Carbon Emissions Reduction	
Target	Five to ten percent (5–10%) reduction in CO ₂ emissions.
Measurement	Carbon footprint calculations based on energy consumption data.

Table 7: P4 resilience KPIs.

Fault Tolerance	
Target	System recovers from node failures within two (2) minutes.
Measurement	Downtime and recovery time metrics after simulating node or network failures.
Scalability	
Target	Maintain performance (latency: under 3 minutes, efficiency: above 90%) as nodes scale up.
Measurement	Validate KPIs under incremental scaling from single node to multi-node deployments.

6.4.3 Validation Environment

The setup of the fourth pilot consists of a distributed environment featuring Edge nodes, cloud orchestration, and IoT sensors. Edge nodes, including RPi devices and industrial Edge servers, are installed across various buildings to form the distributed infrastructure. Cloud orchestration is managed using K8s clusters, which handle workloads, predictive analytics, and global optimization. Additionally, IoT sensors monitor real-time energy metrics such as power consumption, photovoltaic systems output, and market values, ensuring comprehensive data collection and analysis. Table 8, showcases the testing scenarios that will take place on the P4 setup.

Table 8: P4 scenarios for testing.

Real-Time Demand Response	
Scenario	Sudden increase in energy demand (e.g., HVAC usage spikes).
Validation	System's ability to predict demand and redistribute loads efficiently.
Renewable Energy Integration	
Scenario	Variable photovoltaic system generation due to weather conditions.
Validation	Predictive model accuracy and scheduling adaptation to renewable availability.

Fault Simulation	
Scenario	Node or network failures.
Validation	Recovery time, system stability, and effectiveness of redundancy mechanisms.

6.4.4 Comparative Analysis and Evaluation Outcomes

The performance of CODECO is measured against traditional centralized energy management systems. The evaluation focuses on improvements in latency, energy efficiency, and fault tolerance, providing a clear baseline to assess CODECO's advancements. On Table 9 and Table 10 the metrics of comparison can be found as well as the expected outcomes.

Table 9: P4 performance metrics.

Metric	Description
Energy Efficiency Gains	Improvement in energy usage optimization compared to centralized systems (based on percentage).
System Responsiveness	Reduction in decision-making latency during real-time energy events.
Resilience	Time to recover from node failures compared to baseline recovery times.

Table 10: P4 expected performance improvements.

Outcome	Description
Quantified Energy Savings	Report energy efficiency improvements and carbon footprint reductions.
System Scalability Insights	Validate CODECO's performance under scaled deployments.
Real-Time Effectiveness	Demonstrate CODECO's ability to handle real-time energy dynamics with minimal latency.
Fault Tolerance Proof	Highlight system robustness through recovery metrics.

6.5 Summary and Future Work

The energy use-case within the CODECO framework aims to demonstrate measurable improvements in energy efficiency, sustainability, and operational resilience. To assess the effectiveness of the deployed system, a set of KPIs has been defined. These KPIs capture critical metrics such as energy consumption reduction, latency for decision-making, fault tolerance, and scalability. Table 11 consolidates the outcomes achieved during the experimentation, providing a clear overview of the system's performance relative to the defined goals.

Table 11: P4 KPI progress.

Sub-KPI	Measurement Goal	Achieved?	
		Yes	No
Operational number of working nodes	At least ten (10) functional nodes across different locations.	X	
Latency for decision-making	Under three (3) minutes from data ingestion to actionable decision.		X
Network stability	Zero communication breakdowns under normal operating conditions.		X
Fault recovery time	Recovery within two (2) minutes after a node failure.	X	
Scalability performance	Maintain under three (3) minute latency with increasing nodes (up to 15 nodes).		X
Total setup time	Reduction of ten percent (10%) in comparison to K8s.	X	
Energy optimization effectiveness	Five to ten percent (5–10%) reduction in energy consumption across all nodes.		X

Table 12 outlines the sequential tasks that will guide the completion of the energy use-case. The next steps focus on expanding the deployment to additional environments, refining

predictive models, enhancing system resilience, and integrating feedback from stakeholders. These tasks aim to ensure the continuous improvement and scalability of CODECO's implementation while addressing any gaps identified during the progress of P4. The structured approach outlined in Table 12 ensures that the use-case aligns with both project objectives and real-world applicability.

Table 12: P4 task progress.

Task Number	Task Description	Milestones	Expected Outcome
1	Define use-case objectives and KPIs	Objectives and KPIs finalized and documented	Clear scope and measurable goals for the use-case
2	Develop system architecture and deployment methodology	System architecture and methodology reviewed	Comprehensive deployment plan and technical blueprint
3	Procure and configure Edge devices and IoT sensors	Hardware installation completed and tested	Operational Edge nodes with energy monitoring sensors
4	Deploy initial CODECO components (ACM, MDM) in a single node	Single-node deployment validated	Proof of concept validated for a single building
5	Test and validate predictive models for energy forecasting	Predictive models trained and validated	Accurate energy demand and generation forecasting
6	Expand deployment to multiple buildings in the campus	Multi-building deployment operational	Integrated Edge-Cloud orchestration for energy systems
7	Validate real-time decision-making and load balancing	Real-time system performance verified	Improved energy efficiency and reduced latency
8	Scale deployment to additional campuses	Cross-campus orchestration deployed successfully	Demonstrated scalability and cross-campus coordination
9	Conduct fault-tolerance and resilience testing	Recovery mechanisms validated	Reliable operation under node or network failures
10	Perform final evaluation and comparative analysis of KPIs	Evaluation report completed and presented	Comprehensive results showcasing CODECO's impact

7 P5: Wireless AGV Control for Flexible Factories

There is today an increasing need to consider AMRs, of which one example are AGVs in manufacturing environments, to support the heterogeneous and growing demand of material handling and logistics in flexible factory environments.

While current AGV fleets are based on pre-defined task assignment and pre-defined paths, there is an urgent need to provide a more flexible control to support fleets with a larger number of AGVs, and to support an increasing number of tasks/goods to be transported. By reaching a higher level of autonomy, it is possible to increase overall efficiency while reducing operational costs. The integration of wireless technologies to support the control of AGVs, e.g., 5G, Wi-Fi 6/7, becomes highly relevant and shall be explored by CODECO. However, relying on wireless implies also that the control of AGV systems is prone to interference and intermittent connectivity, thus requiring a higher degree of adaptation which a flexible orchestration framework such as CODECO is expected to provide.

CODECO is used to support the decentralization of the applications used to manage the fleet and their assignments, by supporting an energy-efficient automated application workload, across a mobile infrastructure. This is handled two-fold: (i) providing a “better” computation support for the required fleet navigation algorithms, as the emulated mobile robots are based on embedded devices, thus not necessarily having all resources to support all the micro-services of the application workload; (ii) simplifying the setup of applications and their micro-services across a decentralized environment.

7.1 Use-Case Structure

Figure 15 presents the overall P5 system architecture, considering operation within one (1) single cluster. Overall, there is an AGV fleet to be set or running some robotics applications to carry out tasks.

It is therefore assumed that:

- A specific set of applications (robotics application workload(s)) for AGV fleets is available, and there is a user (DEV) that wants to install that application across the fleet, in an automated way.
- An AGV fleet is available (ROS devices).
- The overall AGV fleet is interconnected (via wireless/cellular technologies).
- CODECO is installed and runs on the cluster.

CODECO as a management framework will be triggered for instance due to:

- One (1) or more AGVs may be experiencing issues with connectivity (intermittent connectivity).
- One (1) or more AGVs may be running out of battery.
- One (1) or more AGVs may lack resources to complete a specific task (e.g., lack of memory, energy, etc.).

Two (2) specific user-stories are considered in P5, related with the setup of the robotics applications in the AGV fleet, and to the overall runtime of the installed application and its micro-services.

Figure 15: P5 system architecture, single cluster operation.

Deployment of micro-services in an AGV fleet

As shown in Figure 15, the user DEV (UJ1) wants to deploy a new CODECO offered application in P5 use-case across an AGV fleet and wants also to manage its application workload with K8s/K8s/CODECO. For this purpose, the user starts by accessing the CODECO ACM UI (1) via the available dashboard (AGV controller). The dashboard shall interact with the ACM UI, via a specific customization for the use-case. Hence, via the dashboard the user DEV shall be able to select a pre-defined set of micro-services deployed for the use-case (2). For the initial CODECO AGV App, the UC shall provide a basic set of micro-services available, such as the ones illustrated in Figure 15. For instance, PubSub approach such as Message Queuing Telemetry Transport (MQTT) Sparkplug or Named Data Networking (NDN); micro-service for task handling; micro-service for object detection. Some of these services will be mandatory; some will be optional.

Then, the user is also requested to enter a set of requirements (3), e.g., key requirements such as latency; size of the fleet (how many AGVs to consider); type of communication (e.g., 5G, Wi-Fi); channel aspects, etc. These parameters serve the purpose of creating the so-called CODECO Application model (Yet Another Markup Language – YAML files), which is key to adequately schedule resources to be used.

Once completed, ACM stores this information (Application Model) in CRD format, (4), making it accessible via the usual K8s/K8s methods to other components of CODECO, in alignment with the CODECO CRs/CRDs. SWM starts the initial placement (5). The deployment of the AGV services (ApplicationGroup) is started, being all deployed in a single cluster (1 Pod per worker node; one (1) AGV corresponding to a worker node) set up by default with all involved nodes that are within range at an instant in time, and that may appear later in the radio range of the controller (6).

For the case of an AGV fleet based on multiple remote locations (Phase 2), then ACM shall activate the procedures for federated clusters, instead of deployment on a single cluster. Further development aspects shall be considered during the development of CODECO features for federated clusters (M18-M36).

CODECO shall manage in addition the required network path handling, by taking into consideration aspects such as interference mitigation, channel properties, etc. This shall be

handled via the information collected via NetMA for the wireless interconnections across AGVs (7). If required, routes shall be set to optimize the overall communication (8). The user (DEV) shall be able to observe the existing cluster via a CODECO dashboard (9), and be able to make initial adjustments, if required (9).

AGV Fleet control – Resilient infrastructure

This user journey (UJ2, user MGT) relates with the runtime management of the CODECO AGV Apps. The aim is to assist AGVs in autonomous navigation on indoor, blocked spaces. Key challenges concern energy optimization and support of intermittent connectivity. ICT stakeholders relevant for this use-case are mobile communications and Edge-Cloud providers. For this deployment existing proposals for AGV communication will be investigated, e.g., derived from Verband Deutscher Maschinen und Anlagenbau (VDMA) guidelines and shall consider both a single cluster and a multi-cluster deployment.

On a first phase, a centralized approach will be considered where the central controller has a global perspective on the overall K8s infrastructure (data, compute, network, (1)) which is regularly updated based on data collected via different CODECO components and managed via the CODECO CRs/operators (2, 3). The CODECO PDLC performs, for this specific scenario, an analysis of robustness of the overall graph, and of the existing links in terms of energy consumption across a pair of nodes, as well as in terms of channel conditions, Round Trip Time (RTT) between two nodes (4). It can propose an adaptation of the overall communication infrastructure derived from functional and non-functional network requirements to the SWM scheduler (5) which shall then decide on whether to adapt the overall infrastructure (6). Additional re-scheduling supported by CODECO shall take into consideration aspects such as energy consumption. If an AGV is expected to run out of battery soon, then its micro-services shall be passed (replicated or offloaded) to another suitable AGV, automatically selected by CODECO based on the Application Model requirements provided by the user.

On a second phase, a decentralized approach will be considered, where each AGV shall be responsible to transmit its own perspective of the K8sK8s infrastructure at an instant in time to other AGVs. The infrastructure data (data observability, computation, network) is regularly updated by different CODECO operators (2) to the CODECO control plane, which now shall consist of a multi-master cluster. The selection of three (3) master nodes per cluster, to ensure resilience, shall be done based on NetMA input (1) to ensure a stronger resilience to failures.

The use-case will be validated based on the KPIs proposed in Table 13.

Table 13: P5 KPIs.

KPI Identification (ID)	Description	Sub-KPIs
K1	Operational: scalability aspects, such as number of nodes supported, failure reduction, latency reduction.	K1.1.: Number of nodes in a cluster: at least three (3); total number of nodes: 10; at least three (3) clusters in a federated cluster operation.
		K1.2: Time to completion of a task (latency).
		K1.3: Reduce the overall setup time by circa ten percent (10%).
K2	Strategic: better performance, e.g., improved energy consumption, increased resilience in mobile environments.	K2.1: reduce the number of collisions by circa ten percent (10%).
		K2.2.: Network lifetime increase circa by ten percent (10%).
		K2.3: Reduce the overall energy consumption by around ten percent (10%).

		K2.4: Reduce the overall message exchange required to setup applications by circa ten percent (10%).
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7.2 Deployment Methodologies

The fortiss IIoT Lab CODECO cluster currently comprises one (1) controller (K8s master node) and eight (8) worker nodes. The controller node has been deployed in a Lenovo ThinkPad X280 laptop, and eight (8) worker nodes, two (2) TurtleBot3 MARs¹⁴ and six (6) RPi 4 devices.

For the purpose of this specific use-case, only the TurtleBots and the control node has been considered. For the selection of potential hardware to consider, the requirements were: cost-effectiveness, modularity, ease of customization, compact size, compatibility with the Robotics Operating System v2 (ROS2¹⁵), the choice went to the “MAR TurtleBot3 1”. The configuration of the three devices used in this work is shown in Table 14. The devices are interconnected via Wi-Fi (802.11bg), and private IPs are used in the configuration.

Table 14: P5 basic node configuration.

Node	Operating System	RAM
Controller	Ubuntu 22.04 Long Term Support (LTS), kernel 5.15	15 GiB
Worker nodes	Ubuntu server 22.04 LTS, kernel 5.15	7.6 GiB

Figure 15 presents a single cluster with one (1) master node (K8sK8s and CODECO control plane) and n AGVs (AGV1, ... AGVn) where each AGV is a K8sK8s worker node and a CODECO node. Moreover, the AGV controller is co-located with the CODECO control plane (K8sK8s master node).

The AGV controller may have additional user services, e.g., task handler. The AGVs are represented by Turtlebot3 MARs (AMR).

7.2.1 Deployment of P5 User Journey 1

In this user-story, a developer (DEV, represented in green in Figure 15) wants to deploy a robotics application across the AGV fleet and also to manage its application workload with K8s/CODECO. Then, the user is also requested to enter a set of requirements (3), e.g., key requirements such as latency; size of the fleet (how many AGVs to consider); type of communication (e.g., 5G, Wi-Fi); channel aspects, etc. These parameters serve the purpose of creating the so-called CODECO Application model (CAM).

The dashboard interacts with the CODECO, via a specific customization for the use-case. Hence, via the dashboard the user DEV can select a pre-defined set of micro-services deployed for the use-case (2). For the initial CODECO AGV application, the use-case provides a basic set of micro-services available.

Once completed, CODECO stores this information, making it accessible via the usual K8sK8s methods to other components of CODECO, in alignment with the CODECO and K8sK8s interfacing approach. The CODECO scheduler (SWM) starts the initial application placement (5). The deployment of the AGV application is started, being all deployed in a single cluster (1 Pod per worker node; 1 AGV corresponding to a worker node) set up by default with all

¹⁴ <https://emanual.robotis.com/docs/en/platform/turtlebot3/overview/>

¹⁵ <https://github.com/ros2>

involved nodes that are within range at an instant in time, and that may appear later in the radio range of the controller (6).

CODECO handles in addition the required network path handling, by taking into consideration aspects such as interference mitigation, channel properties, etc (7). If required, routes shall be set to optimize the overall communication (8). The user (DEV) shall be able to observe the existing cluster via a CODECO dashboard (9), and be able to make initial adjustments, if required (9).

To perform evaluation, P5 uses a new service (**Performance evaluation dashboard component**), which assists in the visualization of the obtained results. Experimental results are assessed against K8s. The performance indicators considered (against K8s) are: i) time to deploy an application; ii) messaging overhead; iii) energy consumed.

The robotics application used in the P5 use-case is available via the CODECO GitLab repository¹⁶.

7.2.2 Deployment of P5 User Journey 2

This user journey (user MGT, steps in red) relates with the runtime management of the deployed containerized applications. The aim is to assist AGVs in autonomous navigation on indoor, blocked spaces. Key challenges concern energy optimization and support of intermittent connectivity.

On Phase 1 the use-case considers a centralized approach where the central controller has a global perspective on the overall K8s infrastructure (data, compute, network), (1) which is regularly updated based on data collected via different CODECO components and managed via the CODECO K8s CRs/operators (2, 3). In CODECO, an AI-based engine, the PDLC component performs an analysis of robustness of the overall infrastructure graph (nodes, links) in terms of energy consumption across a pair of nodes, as well as in terms of channel conditions, RTT, between two nodes (4). It can propose an adaptation of the overall communication infrastructure derived from functional and non-functional network requirements to the CODECO SWM scheduler (5) which shall then decide on whether to adapt the overall infrastructure (6). Additional re-scheduling supported by CODECO shall take into consideration aspects such as energy consumption. If an AGV is expected to run out of battery in some time, then its micro-services shall be passed (replicated or offloaded) to another suitable AGV, automatically selected by CODECO based on the Application Model requirements provided by the user.

7.3 Software Customization

7.3.1 Robotics Application Workload

For the proposed use-case, an analysis of existing AGV fleet management tools have been developed. To create an application that could assist the validation of CODECO, in particular creating a proof-of-concept that could serve the analysis of the capability to handle stateful migration, a specific application has been developed for autonomous navigation of AGVs composed of different micro-services: **bringup**; **Simultaneous Localization and Mapping (SLAM)**; **Navigation** which are available via the CODECO Gitlab¹⁷.

¹⁶ <https://gitlab.eclipse.org/eclipse-research-labs/codeco-project/use-cases/p5-amr-manufacturing>

¹⁷ <https://gitlab.eclipse.org/eclipse-research-labs/codeco-project/use-cases/p5-amr-manufacturing/-/tree/main/docker/>

The **bringup** micro-service is responsible for initializing the AGVs core systems. This includes setting up the communication interfaces, starting the necessary ROS2 nodes, and configuring sensors and actuators. It handles the initialization of hardware components, ensuring that all sensors (e.g., LiDAR, cameras), motors (e.g., wheels), and other hardware components are properly connected and operational. It starts the core ROS2 packages and establishes reliable communication between the worker nodes and controller, for remote control and visualization.

SLAM is used for autonomous driving, e.g., to assist robots to explore unknown environments and to be able to build a map by collecting the data from existing sensors. The Google Cartographer¹⁸ is a widely well-known SLAM algorithm, which is also compatible with ROS2. In this work, the AGVs (TurtleBots) lack the processing power necessary for SLAM, so a local Laptop, with the same IP subnet, is used instead for the required SLAM intensive computation. Each AGV handles the bringup process, including motor control and sensor data acquisition, within a Docker container. Data transmission between the AGV and the controller node (laptop) is handled via Data Distribution Service (DDS), which handles the real-time exchange of sensor data and SLAM results. In this setup, the AGV publishes sensor data such as laser scans and odometry via ROS2 topics. These topics are transmitted over the network using DDS to the controller node, where the Cartographer SLAM algorithm runs in a separate Docker container. The controller node subscribes to the sensor data topics and performs the SLAM computations, publishing the resulting map and localization data back to the AGV.

The SLAM Docker image¹⁹ is also available as open-source and uploaded to the CODECO Dockerhub repository.

The **Navigation** micro-service is based on the Navigation System6 (Nav2²⁰), a control system that allows a MAR to autonomously reach a specified goal state, such as a particular position and orientation on a given map. Starting from its current position and using the map and target destination, the navigation system generates a plan to reach the goal. It then issues commands to autonomously guide the robot, ensuring adherence to safety constraints and avoiding any obstacles encountered along the way. Running the Nav2 algorithm for navigation on an AGV with ROS2 using Docker involves a collaborative setup between the AGV and the local laptop which behaves as fleet controller. The controller node subscribes to the topics published by AGV bringup-services, processes the data to build a map using SLAM, and then runs the Nav2 stack for navigation.

The Nav2 stack on the controller node consists of several key nodes, including *amcl* for localization, *planner_server* for path planning, *controller_server* for following the planned path, and *bt_navigator* to manage the navigation behaviour tree. The AGV publishes its sensor data, which the controller node uses to update the map and localize the AGV. The controller node then sends velocity commands back to the AGV to move it along the planned path. This setup allows for efficient and accurate navigation, leveraging the computational power of the controller node while keeping the AGV's processing load manageable.

Based on Navigation, an AGV can be given a script that defines the locations to be reached (fixed poses script) and then the AGVs will follow these poses moving. This is called Waypoint Follower²¹.

To maintain continuous operation, especially in the face of failures such as power depletion, node failure, or high latency, the system can migrate the SLAM workload from one (1) AGV to

¹⁸ <https://google-cartographer-ros.readthedocs.io/en/latest/>

¹⁹ <https://hub.docker.com/r/hecodeco/uc-p5-slam>

²⁰ <https://docs.nav2.org/>

²¹ <https://docs.nav2.org/configuration/packages/configuring-waypoint-follower.html>

another. For this specific work, the use of the k8s Persistent Volume²² (PV) and Persistent Volume Claim (PVC) has been considered, to share data. PV provides a persistent storage solution that can be accessed by any node in the cluster, while PVC ensures that the necessary data, such as the current map, is available to a new selected node which can take over the SLAM task(s) of a node that is running out of battery, or experiencing any other triggering condition for CODECO (as explained in *Section 7.1*).

7.3.2 Dashboard

A dashboard, illustrated in Figure 16, has been deployed in the controller node to assist in the interaction and experimentation. Via the dashboard, users can deploy workloads, monitor the status of nodes and running pods within the cluster effectively. This comprehensive view allows users to oversee the health and performance of the cluster, ensuring that all components are functioning as expected.

The screenshot displays the 'AGV Controller Plane' dashboard. It features a table for 'CODECO Nodes and Pods' with columns for Node Name, Status, and Pods. Below this is a 'Pod Latencies' table with columns for Pod Name, Container Name, and Latency (seconds). The 'Assign Workload to AGVs' section includes dropdown menus for 'Workloads' (set to 'Teleoperation') and 'Turtlebots' (set to 'turtlebot1'), with a 'Deploy' button. At the bottom, the 'Turtlebot Control' section contains buttons for 'forward', 'left', 'stop', 'right', and 'backward'.

Node Name	Status	Pods
master	Ready	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> node-exporter-shq75 (Namespace: monitoring) - Status: Running blackbox-exporter-76b5c44577-igxb4 (Namespace: monitoring) - Status: Running prometheus-operator-7f76ccf69b-sfhpl (Namespace: monitoring) - Status: Running kube-state-metrics-6c664d5dc8-f6kkc (Namespace: monitoring) - Status: Running prometheus-k8s-1 (Namespace: monitoring) - Status: Running prometheus-k8s-0 (Namespace: monitoring) - Status: Running grafana-69f6b485b9-b5qcw (Namespace: monitoring) - Status: Running alertmanager-main-0 (Namespace: monitoring) - Status: Running alertmanager-main-1 (Namespace: monitoring) - Status: Running alertmanager-main-2 (Namespace: monitoring) - Status: Running prometheus-adapter-74894c5547-dlqsq (Namespace: monitoring) - Status: Running prometheus-adapter-74894c5547-b8ksb (Namespace: monitoring) - Status: Running mdm-controller-6ccb984fcb-nvp9d (Namespace: default) - Status: Running netma-controller-7787f576cd-fdvch (Namespace: default) - Status: Running acm-controller-849ddb447-llnxz (Namespace: default) - Status: Running ca-controller-69cf4778cb-wwl9b (Namespace: default) - Status: Running
turtlebot1	Not Ready	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> node-exporter-bb6jw (Namespace: monitoring) - Status: Running
turtlebot2	Ready	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> node-exporter-rbb9m (Namespace: monitoring) - Status: Running

Pod Name	Container Name	Latency (seconds)

Workloads: Teleoperation

Turtlebots: turtlebot1

Deploy

Turtlebot Control

forward left stop right backward

Figure 16: P5 dashboard for Control of the AGVs.

²² <https://kubernetes.io/docs/concepts/storage/persistent-volumes/>

Additionally, the dashboard features a virtual joystick, providing intuitive control over TurtleBots. This virtual joystick allows users to manually manoeuvre TurtleBots, enabling precise navigation and interaction within the environment.

7.4 Evaluation Methodologies

7.4.1 Operational Setup Control

Status	Achieved
Verification	fortiss IIoT Lab (open access infrastructure ²³)

This experimental methodology addresses the overall setup of the use-case in terms of hardware and software, to ensure that all required pre-conditions are met before the system is set to work. It addresses the overall setup of the use-case in terms of hardware and software, to ensure that all required pre-conditions are met before the system is set to work. The aim is to perform control tests to ensure that both the infrastructure and the application are adequately running as well as local and remotely accessible.

The pre-conditions are:

- At least an active cluster is setting, encompassing all Actors.
- The cluster is remotely accessible (ssh).
- AGVs can be easily added or removed.
- The topology and networking conditions are stable.

In this context, P5 counts with two experimental environments:

- The FOR CODECO testbed in the fortiss IIoT Lab.
- An emulation of the cluster/multi-cluster environment in KinD.

7.4.1.1 KinD Environment

The current experimentation uses an emulation of the FOR CODECO cluster in KinD. After setting the topology, the configuration involved deploying a Container Network Interface (CNI) to enable communication between the cluster nodes. Weave Net²⁴ was selected as the CNI due to its capability to handle dynamic, multi-host networking and provide robust network management across the cluster. In CODECO, the default CNI is Multus²⁵.

Prometheus²⁶ has been deployed as metrics server (requirement in CODECO). Furthermore, Grafana²⁷ was deployed for monitoring the performance and health of the K8s cluster. Prometheus gets, via CODECO, monitoring of resources at a node and networking level from worker nodes and from the application workload (application, pod and node level). Grafana has been used to visualize the Prometheus metrics, providing a user-friendly interface for monitoring the performance and operational status of the cluster.

7.4.1.2 fortiss IIoT Lab CODECO Environment

After the validation of the ROS2 system within the K8s environment, the next step was to evaluate the performance of the overall system for the proposed application workload, when considering CODECO and specific trigger conditions for CODECO to act (e.g., node has no

²³ <https://www.fortiss.org/en/research/fortiss-labs/detail/iiot-lab>

²⁴ <https://github.com/weaveworks/weave>

²⁵ <https://github.com/k8snetworkplumbingwg/multus-cni>

²⁶ <https://github.com/prometheus-operator/kube-prometheus>

²⁷ <https://grafana.com/>

battery). The current version of CODECO, the "CODECO Basic Operation Components and Toolkit version 2.0" [10] has been used and installed following the steps described in the accompanied report. The different CODECO components provide specific resources within their own namespaces, starting by "he-codeco", for instance, he-codeco-acm, he-codeco-netma, he-codeco-mdm, he-codeco-pdlc, and he-codeco-swm.

7.4.2 Application Workload Control

Status	Achieved
Verification	fortiss IIoT Lab (open access infrastructure ²⁸); videos in YouTube

The aim is to assess the accuracy and completeness of the application workload running in the AGVs. An initial AGV workload relates with task assignments for AGVs, where the AGVs shall rely on SLAM, to move to a specific location for a specific period. The aspects to assess were:

- The right location has been reached (accuracy in meters).
- Repeatability, meaning that the robot can reach the location with similar accuracy, after several repeats.
- Scalability, meaning that the robot accuracy is the same for smaller and larger spaces.

7.4.3 Deployment of an Application and its Micro-Services

Status	Ongoing (Achieved in KinD)
Verification	fortiss IIoT Lab (open access infrastructure); videos in YouTube; publication (Under submission, Jan 2025.)

Relates with P5 user journey 1, focused on the deployment of micro-services (containerized applications). Performance indicators will be:

- Time to setup the application.
- Messaging overhead.
- Energy consumed.

Scenario variability will take into consideration features such as:

- Available nodes (small, medium, large; Received Signal Strength Indicator – RSSI, etc.)
- Size of the application and of its datasets.
- Node battery capability.

7.4.4 Runtime Management Evaluation

Status	Ongoing (achieved in KinD, latency); proof-of-concept achieved
Verification	fortiss IIoT Lab (open access infrastructure); videos in YouTube; publication (Under submission, Jan 2025.)

This methodology has as basis the scenarios of P5 user journey 2. This user journey aims to assist AGVs in autonomous navigation on indoor, blocked spaces. Key challenges concern energy optimization and support of intermittent connectivity. Key performance aspects to evaluate are:

- Resilience (reduction in collisions).

²⁸ <https://www.fortiss.org/en/research/fortiss-labs/detail/iiot-lab>

- Energy consumption.
- Latency, RTT between two nodes.
- Latency, time to completion of AGV tasks.
- Latency during re-scheduling. If an AGV is expected to run out of battery soon, then its micro-services shall be passed (replicated or offloaded) to another suitable AGV, automatically selected by CODECO based on the Application Model requirements provided by the user.

7.5 Summary and Future Work

The current work is being defined based on the proposed timeline for the use-case. The overall plan and status are provided in Table 15 and Table 16.

Table 15: P5 task progress.

Task Id	Task	Deadline	Status M24
P5.1	Use-case design	M1-M3	Achieved M3
P5.2	Scenario setup fortiss IIoT Labs	M6-M9	Achieved M9
P5.3	Integration of CODECO components	M10-M24	Achieved M12
P5.4	Work Package 5 (WP5). Integration, deployment and experiments Work Package 7 (WP7) – community engagement	M13-M18	Ongoing Single-cluster, M28
P.5.5	Refinements and demos single cluster Start integration of multi-cluster Analyse (WP7) possibility to perform demos in operational environments	M20-M24	Achieved M24
P5.6	Complete experimentation single cluster	M20-M28	Ongoing
P5.7	Define multi-cluster design	M24	Achieved
P5.8	Complete CODECO integration in the testbed	M27	
P5.8	Start multi-cluster experiments	M30	
P5.9	Refinements, experiments, demos	M25-M36	
P5.10	Final demos	M36	

Table 16: P5 KPI progress.

Sub-KPI	Measurement Goal	Achieved?	
		Yes	No
Operational number of AGVs in a cluster	At least five (5).	X	
Time to completion of a task (latency)	Reduction by twenty percent (20%) in comparison to an environment without CODECO.	X	
Reduction in the number of collisions	Reduction by at least percent (10%).		X
Network lifetime	Increase in ten percent (10%) of the network energy lifetime.		X
Total setup time	Reduction of ten percent (10%) in comparison to K8s.	X	
Energy consumed during setup	Reduction of ten percent (10%) in comparison to K8s.	X	
Messaging overhead	Reduction by twenty percent (20%) in comparison to an environment without CODECO.		X

8 P6: Automated Crownstone Application Deployment for Smart Buildings

The sixth pilot intends to use CODECO to automate the deployment and management of a Crownstone network. By automating these processes, CODECO enables the Crownstone network to remain flexible, efficient, and scalable in a dynamic environment.

A Crownstone network is a network of several types of devices deployed in an office environment, which introduces several new functionalities to this environment: indoor localisation of people, occupancy monitoring, automated switching and dimming of lights, demand-side energy management, and several new sensing and actuation functionalities. Figure 17 visualises a Crownstone Node inside a power outlet.

Figure 17: P6 Crownstone node inside a power outlet.

The entire use-case revolves around the aspect of automated deployment of applications. The main user benefiting from automated deployment is primarily the facility manager wishing to deploy applications in the office as well as to define service levels for those applications.

In a Crownstone network, applications often involve multiple interacting components: a part in the Crownstone Cloud, a part on the Crownstone Hubs, and even a part running inside Crownstone nodes. Typically, low-level sensor data processing is done inside the nodes. The Hubs, which manage a collection of nodes from which they receive data, typically perform higher-level analyses on this data and share the outcomes with the cloud. The cloud enables the connection to other Crownstone networks, the internet and smartphone apps.

In the context of CODECO, specific attention is given to automated deployment based on topology-based redeployment (changes in the Crownstone network, e.g. Crownstone nodes or hubs added or removed) and occupancy-based redeployment (changes in the presence of persons in the office, their number and movements).

8.1 Use-Case Structure

Before the structure of the use-case is explained, first the main technical challenges that are foreseen in the realisation of the use-case must be analysed. These are the involvement of Crownstone nodes, the awareness within the cluster of the Crownstone network topology, and the availability of occupancy information in the cluster.

8.1.1 Crownstone Nodes Involvement

The first challenge in this use-case is the involvement of Crownstone nodes in the realm of CODECO (K8s). Since Crownstones lack a TCP/IP stack, virtual Kubernetes worker nodes are employed as proxies to integrate them seamlessly into the K8s ecosystem. On the

Crownstone hubs, so-called Virtual Kubelets (VKs²⁹) are automatically installed by CODECO to virtually represent a single Crownstone node. The virtual Kubelet, consequently, acts as a virtual worker node in the cluster, on which CODECO can deploy applications, in this case, micro-apps. This way, there are virtually introduced Crownstone nodes in the realm of CODECO.

8.1.2 Crownstone Network Topology Awareness

The second challenge is to make sure CODECO is enabled to dynamically adapt and optimize the deployment of applications based on information about the network topology, thereby enabling topology-based (re)deployment. Ideally, the cluster needs to:

- be able to determine which hub can communicate with each Crownstone node.
- ensure each Crownstone node is equipped with the correct micro-app necessary to support its intended functionality.
- identify the capabilities of each Crownstone node, including the sensors or actuators it is directly connected to or those within its communication range.

Note that the third aspect is considered nice-to-have, but not necessary for the defined user-stories and future demonstration scenarios.

8.1.3 Occupancy Awareness

Finally, the cluster needs somehow to be enabled to use occupancy information in its decision-making process. Work needs to be done on several strategies to get this kind of data available in the cluster. The most important observation here is that the presence of people considerably influences the network statistics of the Crownstone mesh network. These statistics are readily available in the network, as the Crownstone nodes report to their hubs about packet loss rates and other statistics. The aim is to make this data available to CODECO. Also, there is a need to provide direct occupancy data to the cluster as a second option. This information, however, is currently only available in the cloud (based on the report of smartphone apps of office users) and not in the Edge.

8.1.4 Technical Overview of the Use-Case

A typical setup of a Crownstone network can be found in Figure 18. Various Crownstone nodes (depicted with the Crownstone logos) form a mesh (note: the nodes can also communicate with each other, which is not depicted). Each node, however, “belongs” to a hub, on which a virtual Kubelet takes care of its representation as a worker node. The hubs themselves (depicted with a RPi logo) are also worker nodes, and communicate with the Crownstone Cloud, which runs on the only worker node in the cloud, typically an Amazon Web Services (AWS) server instance.

²⁹ <https://virtual-kubelet.io/>

Figure 18: P6 typical setup of a Crownstone network.

CODECO is not shown in this figure, but it is inferred that it is located in the control plane in the Cloud (the Crownstone cloud runs on a worker node in the cloud) and in the components running on the three real worker nodes (Crownstone cloud server and hubs). A detailed overview of the technical setup of the use-case is given below in Figure 19.

Figure 19: Technical setup of use-case P6.

8.2 Deployment Methodologies

The use-case will be deployed as depicted in Figure 18. In this figure, the map shown is actually the map of the ALM main office in Rotterdam. The use-case will be executed on one (1) server in the AWS cloud (Crownstone Cloud), two (2) RPi 5 minicomputers (Crownstone Hubs) and with at least twelve (12) Crownstone nodes installed in the power outlets of the building. This constitutes the main setup of ALM playground environment. In principle, the control plane will run on a separate server in the cloud, but there is a possibility to combine it with the Crownstone Cloud instance on a single server.

Note that the exact position of each Crownstone node in the office is not determined in advance: some of them will be mounted in power outlets mounted in the office walls, others might be deployed as plugs into extension cords. Similarly, the exact distribution of Virtual Kubelets for the Crownstone nodes on the hubs is not determined in advance as well: rather, it results from the actual decisions made by the CODECO framework which hub is most suitable to act as the host for the representational Virtual Kubelet with respect to visibility and load balancing on the hubs.

8.2.1 User-Story 1: Automated Application Deployment

The intention of this user-story is to provide an easy method for the initial deployment of a Crownstone network. This user-story is a baseline, which enables the other two more interesting user stories. Simply put, the CODECO framework is enabled to automatically deploy the Crownstone Cloud components, the Crownstone Hub components, and the micro-apps on the Crownstone nodes, based on a configuration file (YAML). The trigger for CODECO consists of the initiation (start-up) of the system after all hardware components have been installed in the office environment and added to the Crownstone network via the Crownstone smartphone app.

8.2.2 User-story 2: Topology-Based Application (Re)deployment

Starting point for this user-story is an office equipped with a K8s cluster consisting of a CODECO control plane, two (2) hubs and several pre-installed Crownstones, and after user-

story 1 has been executed, i.e. all components are installed and CODECO is maintaining the desired state of the Crownstone network.

The trigger of this user-story consists of the installation of a new piece of hardware in the Crownstone network: a new Crownstone node is added to the office by plugging it into a desired socket and configuring it via a mobile phone (including setting the appropriate keys). The mesh sniffer on one or both hubs detects messages from the previously un-known Crownstone node. These newly detected messages function as a trigger for the CODECO framework.

The CODECO framework responds to the trigger by expanding its cluster. It automatically installs and deploys the necessary pods to integrate the new Crownstone in the network. It also updates other existing daemon configurations, ensuring seamless functionality within the network. To achieve this, CODECO performs a series of predefined actions to integrate the new Crownstone into the cluster. These actions include determining the best hub to host the Virtual Kubelet, deploying a Virtual Kubelet pod for the new Crownstone on the hub and updating the relay agent to facilitate communication.

8.2.3 User-story 3: Occupancy-Based Application (Re)deployment

Starting point for this user-story is an office equipped with a K8s cluster consisting of a CODECO control plane, two (2) hubs and several pre-installed Crownstones, and after user-story 1 has been executed, i.e. all components are installed and CODECO is maintaining the desired state of the Crownstone network.

The trigger of this user-story is an indirect one: the increasing or decreasing presence/movement of users in the room causes deviations in BLE network statistics, such as fluctuations in signal strength, packet loss, broadcast conflicts, or latency spikes. The Virtual Kubelets are reporting this information to CODECO. When these metrics exceed predefined thresholds/optimal state, a trigger is generated.

The CODECO framework, by leveraging its NetMA component to process the deviations detected in the BLE network statistics, can identify the changes in network conditions. CODECO evaluates the increased occupancy (in terms of the network statistics) and initiates appropriate actions to ensure the Crownstone network operates efficiently and remains in an optimal state. These actions include executing specific micro-app actions to optimize the BLE mesh, such as removing micro-apps that are too expensive in terms of processing time or adjusting micro-apps that produce too much mesh traffic.

8.3 Software Customization

The typical software customization actions needed for this use-case have been explained previously. They consist of the involvement of Crownstone nodes, the awareness within the cluster of the Crownstone network topology, and the availability of occupancy information in the cluster.

The biggest challenge of this use-case was integrating the non-IP Crownstone device into K8s to enable orchestration by CODECO. To address this, Virtual Kubelets were exploited. A Virtual Kubelet acts as a virtual Kubernetes worker node that can be deployed as a pod on the hub worker node. This Virtual Kubelet pod registers with the K8s cluster as a standard worker node, allowing pods to be deployed on it like any other node. However, the follow-up actions differ significantly.

Each Virtual Kubelet represents a Crownstone node in a proxy-like manner, providing it with an IP interface and linking it to a custom API. This approach effectively incorporates a Crownstone device into the K8s cluster. The custom API is responsible for translating K8s /CODECO commands into actions that initiate BLE communication with the non-IP Crownstone devices. Additionally, Crownstones can report back information or data to the Virtual Kubelet via BLE. This seamless communication enables full integration of non-IP Crownstone devices into the K8s ecosystem, empowering CODECO to orchestrate them effectively.

8.4 Evaluation Methodologies

Evaluation of the user-stories mainly concerns user-stories 2 and 3, as they imply that user-story 1 functions as expected. Therefore, there is a need to define an elaborate evaluation methodology for user-stories 2 and 3, and to use a simple evaluation methodology for user-story 1.

8.4.1 User-Story 1: Automated Application Deployment

The first user-story relates to defined KPIs 1 and 4:

- 1: Effort needed to deploy and expand local smart buildings infrastructures.
- 4: Ability to monitor and verify the correct behaviour of a Crownstone sphere.

For KPI 1, there is a need to do a manual installation of the entire network first and measure the time it takes. Then, the installation by means of CODECO will be done again to measure another time, the time it takes to do a full setup. It is expected that the automated initial deployment will reduce the overall time needed to do the complete setup.

For KPI 4, basically, the evaluation can be done by observing the correct achievement of the desired state at initiation of the Crownstone network: no errors occur during the initial setup of the cluster. The Crownstone dashboard (currently a set of command-line tools, to be equipped at a later stage with a web interface) shows that all Crownstones are active in the network and the micro-apps are running. In the context of this user-story, micro-apps will be developed that actively communicate their running state such that it is visible via the Crownstone dashboard.

8.4.2 User-Story 2: Topology-Based Application (Re)deployment

The second user-story also relates to defined KPIs 1 and 4:

- 1: Effort needed to deploy and expand local smart buildings infrastructures.
- 4: Ability to monitor and verify the correct behaviour of a Crownstone sphere.

For KPI 1, the same method will be applied as in user-story 1, i.e., a manual installation of an additional single Crownstone node will be done and measure the time it takes. Then, the same scenario will be done one more time by means of CODECO, and, again, measure the time it takes to do a full set-up. It is expected that the automated addition of the new Crownstone node in the network, as well as the redeployment of applications if needed, will reduce the overall time needed to install an additional Crownstone node in the network.

In the context of KPI 4, if all goes well, the Crownstone dashboard will dynamically update to reflect the addition of the new Crownstone, providing a real-time view of the updated cluster.

The dashboard overview of the deployed micro-apps will also dynamically update to reflect changes in deployment. Finally, the network statistics dashboard will display altered network statistics over time, as an additional Crownstone node in the network usually has implications

for the network statistics. As an additional method, after the installation of a Crownstone node, the newly installed device can be removed from the socket, after which it becomes unreachable and stops providing data as a worker node. This event provides a trigger visible in the Dashboard.

8.4.3 User-Story 3: Occupancy-Based Application (Re)deployment

The third user-story relates to defined KPIs 2 and 3:

- 2: Effort needed to develop and deploy distributed Edge-to-cloud AI applications.
- 3: Effort needed to reconfigure far-Edge data processing applications.

Both KPIs primarily relate to the deployment of micro-apps on the Crownstone nodes, as well as AI components on the hubs processing the data originating from these micro-apps, e.g. pre-processed data from BLE sensors connected to the Crownstone nodes.

For KPI 2, the main issue is the deployment of applications in the Crownstone network, as the development time as such will not change by means of CODECO. The deployment and redeployment of those apps, however, can be easily evaluated following the schemes explained in the previous user stories.

In KPI 3, it is not so much the reconfiguration of the applications themselves, but rather the availability of new types of triggers to perform such reconfiguration: in this user-story this is occupancy within the office environment. The effort needed to reconfigure applications based on occupancy mainly lies in the fact that up to now, this was a manual activity which required to continuously monitor the actual occupancy in the office, which makes occupancy-based (re)deployment scenarios practically impossible.

For KPI 3, it is expected that statistics will become available via the CODECO framework (e.g. logs of desired state management activity) that allow us to observe the changes applied whenever the occupancy in the office changes. In order to evaluate this a manual influence and monitoring of the occupancy in the office will be done, and then CODECO will be observed in order to find out if it is triggered to perform certain redeployment actions to maintain the desired state in the Crownstone network.

8.5 Summary & Future Work

Table 17 describes the sub-KPIs and the corresponding measurement goals regarding P6. It also outlines the progress of achieving the KPIs for P6.

Table 17: P6 KPI progress.

Sub-KPI	Measurement Goal	Achieved?	
		Yes	No
Allow centralized initialisation of a complete sphere on the cloud, optional hubs and the Crownstones in the sphere.	Sphere is approachable in the dashboard on the cloud and the app.	X	
Allow changes in the number of Crownstones and hubs in the sphere.	Reduction by twenty percent (20%) in comparison to an environment without CODECO.		X
Orchestrate a deployment of micro-apps over a set of Crownstones with CODECO tooling in the cloud for a sphere.	Changes to the control file or structure for the deployment tooling are generated within the app.	X	
Deploy a micro-app through CODECO tooling over Crownstones in a sphere.	If the micro-apps are arriving and running on the Crownstones.		X
Deploy a micro-app through CODECO tooling to one or more hubs.	Microapp is running on the hub.	X	

Monitor the distribution of micro-apps in a sphere.	Actual insight in the proper functioning and operation of all micro-apps.		X
Monitor the data streams deployed by the proxy agents of the micro-apps.	As micro-apps generally add new data streams to the existing sphere data, this can and must be made measurable.	X	

At this moment, ALM has completed the work on the software customization and has a functional setup with a K8s cluster deploying Crownstone cloud, hub and node components. The Virtual Kubelet infrastructure has been completed as well. Currently, ALM is working mainly on getting the CODECO components running in the test environment, in order to build the necessary trigger infrastructure and start testing for the three (3) user-stories in the ALM office environment in Rotterdam. During the final year of the project, it is expected to complete the CODECO integration until March 2025, to test and get the user-stories functional until May 2025, and to do a first demonstration around June 2025.

Finally, around April 2025, the design of the multi-cluster setup will begin. The aim is to connect two different locations in the ALM office building in Rotterdam and managing two Crownstone networks, each being a separate cluster, in relation with each other. This will yield a second and final demonstration in November 2025.

9 Plan for the Demonstration of Use-cases

An important part of WP5 is dedicated to the demonstration of the functionalities of CODECO by means of the use-cases. While Task 5.3 focuses on lab experimentation, Task 5.4 is dedicated precisely to the demonstrations of the use-cases. During the first twenty-four (24) months of the project, the use-cases have already started preparing for their demonstrations, as the previous sections show: they have highlighted the way in which CODECO plays a role in the pilots and described the way their applications are deployed and orchestrated by the CODECO framework. In Task 5.4, more details will be provided about the proper execution of the demonstration as an event. For the final year, a proper planning of the different demonstrations is needed in order to make them as effective as possible.

The use-case leaders have already started filling in their demonstration plans based on the template distributed to them as included in Annex 1, providing them with a framework to specify in an articulated way exactly how the demonstration event will be held. In the remainder of this section, the plan for Task 5.4 is specified by detailing the four (4) phases carried out in the last year of the project: demonstration plans and environment setup, event preparation, demonstration execution, and result dissemination and evaluation.

9.1 Phase 1: Detailed Demonstration Plans and Environment Setup

Period	M19 – M26
Results	Detailed demonstration plans are ready (Pilot leads). Environment setup (for first demonstrations) is ready (Pilot leads). Overall demonstration planning is ready (Task 5.4 lead).

In the first phase, detailed demonstration plans are specified, indicating for each use-case the number of demonstrations planned (if more than one), an overall timeline for those demonstrations, and for each demonstration a detailed plan highlighting the technical setup of the demonstration, the demonstration scenarios, the event setup and detailed timeline, and dependencies, risks and mitigations. Annex 1 “Use-Case Demonstration Plan” (attached to this deliverable) serves as the basis for the detailed demonstration plans..

The environment setup and demonstration scenarios are part of an overall demonstration design. The general technical setup covers the location (including a map of the environment), the equipment that will be involved and installed in the environment, and which applications will run during the demonstration. The demonstration scenarios provide more detail to the user-stories: they specify which stakeholders are involved in the scenario and provide a complete script for it, i.e. a stepwise description of the scenario specifying exactly what is expected to happen during the demonstration. Typical examples are “user walks into room”, “robot indicates almost empty battery”. Important here is to indicate the expected role of CODECO, when, in the script, CODECO is expected to act based on certain triggers and what can then be observed of this. Finally, the demonstration script needs to be related to the KPIs specified for the use-case and needs to indicate how the observations during the demonstration highlight the achievement of those KPIs.

Based on the input from the various use-case leads, the Task 5.4 lead creates an overall time plan for all demonstrations in order to ensure that the entire plan is consistent, well-planned and feasible.

9.2 Phase 2: Event Preparation

Period	M27 – M33
Results	Announcements made, invites and press releases done (Pilot leads). Final agenda for the demonstrations is ready (Pilot leads). Detailed demonstration script is ready (Pilot leads).

In Phase 2, the demonstration events are properly prepared, based on the detailed demonstration plans. These plans cover typically aspects like the date and time of the event, organisers, agenda, who needs to be invited on-site or online, etc. The pilot leads ensure that announcements of the demonstration events are made in time and press releases are done. Next to this, the final agenda of the demonstration events will be prepared, as well as a detailed demonstration script with all roles properly filled in. The agenda should leave room for a concise introduction of the CODECO project and its objectives, as well as for evaluation and time for questions from the audience. The demonstration script should highlight whether the audience can play an active role during the demonstration, e.g. halting a robot or walking through an office environment. Finally, it is important to highlight in what way the events will be recorded, where specific attention needs to be given to the observation of the role of CODECO in the demonstration.

9.3 Phase 3: Demonstration Execution

Period	M29 – M35
Results	Execution of first demonstration (Pilot leads). Environment setup (for final demonstration) is ready (Pilot leads). Execution of final demonstration (Pilot leads). Overall coordination is done (Task 5.4 lead).

During Phase 3, the demonstrations are executed according to the plan. The project demands at least one (1) demonstration per use-case. If multiple demonstrations for a use-case are planned, the environment setup might need to be revised for the final demonstration, which then needs to take place during this phase. As the actual demonstration events require a smooth execution, all dependencies on others (e.g., other partners in the project, the organisation owning the venue where the demonstration takes place, or external organisations) need to be known and managed. These dependencies are included in the detailed demonstration plans for each use-case as prepared in Phase 1. The Task 5.4 lead helps in executing this overall coordination where possible.

9.4 Phase 4: Result Dissemination and Evaluation

Period	M31 – M36
Results	Individual demonstration reports are ready (Pilot leads). Recordings (videos) of demonstrations are collected (Pilot leads). Evaluation reports are ready (Pilot leads). D5.5 “Use-case Deployment and Demonstrations v2.0” are completed (Task 5.4 lead).

The final phase consists of making sure all demonstration materials and results are collected: attendant lists, demonstration scripts, evaluation reports, dissemination materials, video recordings, etc. These materials are collected and summarized in individual demonstration reports per use-case. The Task 5.4 lead will use all materials collected to publish an update of D5.5 “Use-case Deployment and Demonstrations”. This task will be carried out with due consultation of other work packages, in particular Work Package 6 (WP6), to make sure the deliverable serves its intended dissemination purpose as an evaluation report showing the innovative qualities of the CODECO framework and other major outcomes of the project.

10 Summary and Next Steps

The work presented in this deliverable has illustrated the framework's versatility and effectiveness in a variety of scenarios, as evidenced by the substantial progress made in the deployment and validation of CODECO's use-cases. Each use-case has demonstrated the potential of CODECO to support innovative applications at the Edge-Cloud continuum, improve operational efficiency, and enhance resource utilization, from smart monitoring of public infrastructure to decentralized energy management. The framework's adaptability to address real-world challenges in a variety of domains, such as urban mobility, industrial automation, and smart building management, is underscored by the findings.

The technical feasibility of CODECO has been validated by the deployment methodologies and evaluation metrics implemented in the pilots, which have also yielded valuable insights into its scalability and performance. The pilots have effectively demonstrated CODECO's aptitude for real-time adaptation, workload migration, and dynamic scheduling in a variety of conditions through targeted experimentation. These results confirm CODECO's readiness for a wider range of applications and enable the advancement of its adoption.

In the future, the framework should be refined to address the gaps that have been identified, and full-scale demonstrations will be prepared. The following are key priorities:

- **Improving Scalability:** Increasing the capacity of multi-cluster deployments to accommodate larger and more intricate deployments across a variety of environments.
- **Performance Optimization:** Enhancing energy efficiency and reducing latency by fine-tuning system components, such as network management and privacy-preserving learning.
- **Strengthening Resilience:** The implementation of sophisticated fault-tolerance mechanisms to guarantee uninterrupted operation in dynamic and unpredictable scenarios.
- **Demonstration Planning:** Coordinating initiatives to display CODECO's capabilities through comprehensive pilot demonstrations, with a focus on its transformative impact on specific domains.

The final deliverable will be enhanced by the results of these subsequent steps, which are consistent with CODECO's overarching vision of fostering innovation in Edge-Cloud orchestration and facilitating the development of sustainable, intelligent, and adaptable systems.

10.1 Application of CODECO Across the Use-Cases

This section emphasizes that each CODECO component is engineered with distinct functionalities that are actively employed by the CODECO pilots and serve distinct purposes. These functionalities are customized to meet the system's distinctive requirements and objectives, thereby guaranteeing its overall efficiency and operational effectiveness. The functionalities associated with each CODECO component are summarized in Tables Table 18, Table 20, Table 22, Table 24, and Table 26 to provide a comprehensive overview, highlighting their individual roles and contributions to the pilot operations. Following each one of the tables, Tables Table 19, Table 21, Table 23, Table 25, and Table 27, are showing the usage of each of CODECO's functionalities by the use-cases marked with an "X". A more comprehensive analysis of CODECO's functionalities can be found in CODECO's Deliverable: "D10: CODECO Technological Guidelines, Reference Architecture, and Open-source Ecosystem Design" [2].

Table 18: ACM functionalities.

Functionality ID	Description
ACM-1	Installation of the entire CODECO framework.
ACM-2	Deploy custom applications across CEI (Cloud-Edge-IoT) in an efficient way.
ACM-3	Specifies target performance profiles that are used in PDLC to meet a specific level of greenness or resilience.

Table 19: ACM functionalities applied in the CODECO use-cases.

Functionality ID	P1	P2	P3	P4	P5	P6
ACM-1	X	X	X	X	X	X
ACM-2	X	X	X		X	X
ACM-3	X	X	X	X	X	

Table 20: PDLC functionalities.

Functionality ID	Description
PDLC-1	Provides an estimate on the overall system stability based on privacy-preserving decentralised learning approaches.
PDLC-2	Provides an aggregated cost view of a specific target performance profile for the available infrastructure.

Table 21: PDLC functionalities applied in the CODECO use-cases.

Functionality ID	UC1	UC2	UC3	UC4	UC5	UC6
PDLC-1	X	X	X		X	
PDLC-2	X	X	X	X	X	

Table 22: SWM functionalities.

Functionality ID	Description
SWM-1	Initial placement of workloads based on the application/user QoS requirements.
SWM-2	Dynamic placement of application workloads (re-scheduling).
SWM-3	Application workload deployment and re-deployment.
SWM-4	Application workload migration.

Table 23: SWM functionalities applied in the CODECO use-cases.

Functionality ID	P1	P2	P3	P4	P5	P6
SWM-1	X	X	X	X	X	X
SWM-2	X	X	X	X	X	X
SWM-3	X	X	X	X	X	X
SWM-4	X	X	X	X	X	

Table 24: NetMA functionalities.

Functionality ID	Description
NETMA-1	Provides network awareness.
NETMA-2	Handles secure connectivity across pods.

Table 25: NetMA functionalities applied in the CODECO use-cases.

Functionality ID	P1	P2	P3	P4	P5	P6
NETMA-1	X	X	X	X	X	X
NETMA-2	X		X	X	X	

Table 26: MDM functionalities.

Functionality ID	Description
MDM-1	Provides metrics related to how fresh the data processed by pod is (freshness, age of information).
MDM-2	Provides metrics related to the level of compliance of the pod given where it is running (compliance).
MDM-3	Provides metrics related to how robust the execution of the pod is where it is running (portability).

Table 27: MDM functionalities applied in the CODECO use-cases.

Functionality ID	UC1	UC2	UC3	UC4	UC5	UC6
MDM-1	X	X				
MDM-2	X					X
MDM-3	X					

10.2 Future Directions for Use-Case Implementations

The final version of this deliverable will be available on the 36th month of CODECO's lifespan. The deliverable is primarily concentrated on the deployment of the use-cases on experimentation environments in the current version. The primary focus is on the specific adjustments that each use-case must make in order to be deployed on a cluster with CODECO. This is necessary to either validate the advantages of CODECO or demonstrate its disadvantages. Additionally, this version presents an examination of the structure of the use-cases employed in the validation of CODECO, as well as the distinct methodologies employed in each pilot.

The pilots will be able to redeploy their services on their premises with the final CODECO version, as CODECO's multi-cluster workflow is currently under development. Thus, from now on, the demonstrations are the major objectives of the use-cases and coordination thereof will be done by ALM. The next release of this deliverable will contain demonstration and evaluation reports showing that the innovations of CODECO have been effectively demonstrated during the demo events.

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Annex 1: Use-Case Demonstration Plan Template

The annex provides the generic demonstration plan template which is being used by the use-cases in WP5, T5.4, as explained in section 9 of this deliverable. The aim is to present the overall structure being requested to the CODECO use-cases. The demonstration specification covers all aspects related to the demonstration: demonstration design, setup, involvement of stakeholders, interviews, etc.

1. Demonstration design

1.1. Technical setup

Present the general technical setup of your demonstration, including the following elements:

- Where will the demonstration take place?
- A map of the location (if applicable)
- What equipment will be involved / installed?
- Which applications will run on the equipment?

2. Demo scenario(s)

Provide details of the demonstration scenario(s), including the following elements per scenario:

- A list of stakeholders involved in the scenario, e.g., user, service provider, etc.
- A stepwise description of the scenario, e.g., “user walks into room,” “robot indicates almost empty battery,” etc. Make sure you include the expected role of CODECO in the demonstration, when you expect CODECO to act based on certain triggers, what can then be observed and in which way.
- Indicate which KPIs as defined for CODECO are thereby highlighted in your demonstration.

3. Setup and execution

3.1. Event setup

Present the organisational setup of the demonstration event, including the following elements:

- When will the event(s) take place?
- Who will organise the event(s) and run the demonstrations (real names)
- Who will be the audience (who will you invite for the event(s))
- In what way will you announce the event(s)
- What will be the duration of the event(s)
- Indicate a draft agenda for the event, including welcome, introduction, execution of demonstration scenarios, evaluation, time for questions etc.
- How will you involve the audience in the event(s), think of a role in the actual demonstration as stakeholders, a role in the evaluation (interview), etc.
- Will the event(s) be recorded? In what way?

3.2. Timeline

Provide a clear timeline (preferably in the shape of a GANNT chart) for your demonstration, from preparation and announcement via the actual day of the event(s) up to evaluation. If the actual time of the demonstration is currently unknown, define the timeline in a relative manner, e.g. week 1: announcement and invitation of audience, reservation of required locations, week 3 setup of hardware, testing of demonstration scenarios, etc.

4. Dependencies, risks and mitigations

4.1. Dependencies

Highlight any dependencies on others: other partners in the project (involved e.g. in the software development of your demo), your own organisation (e.g. other departments granting access to certain rooms for demonstration purposes), external organisations (e.g. government blocking a road, bus company providing one or more buses), etc. Indicate where in the technical setup and where in the timeline they are needed.

4.2. Risks and mitigations

Based on the dependencies or other information, provide a table with risks and mitigations. The table should indicate in what way you will be able to deliver a successful demonstration event even if some things go wrong.

You may also include (if applicable) a separate risk table, indicating 1. risk, 2. likelihood (1=low, 10=high), 3. impact (1=low, 10=high) and 4. priority, as the starting point for a list of risks and mitigations.

Risk	Mitigation
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